

Project Valuation Reference Dataset

**Companies from Major US and European Indices,
Grouped by Sector and Industry**

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September 2025**

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Summary

This document presents a list of securities traded on American and European stock exchanges, with reference to September 28, 2025, covering the main indices of Nasdaq, Standard & Poor's, and several European financial markets. The aim is to provide a basis for studying the economic viability of mechanical engineering projects, facilitating the identification of listed companies in relevant sectors and industries.

The sectoral and industrial classification used is based on the Yahoo Finance taxonomy, complemented by a methodological adaptation inspired by the Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS). This adaptation introduces intermediate levels of organization (sub-sectors and super-industries) and a five-digit hierarchical coding system designed to facilitate data analysis and filtering.

The document is intended for educational purposes, allowing students and researchers to use benchmark financial indicators – such as the Beta factor – in the comparative evaluation of projects.

1. Introduction

This document presents a list of securities traded on various stock exchanges, belonging to the main American and European stock indices, with reference to the date of September 28, 2025.

The following indices were considered:

United States of America: Nasdaq-100, Nasdaq Composite, Dow Jones Industrial Average, S&P 500, S&P MidCap 400, S&P SmallCap 600 and Russel 1000;

Europe: DAX, CAC, AEX, BEL, and PSI.

The main objective of this document is to support the study of the economic feasibility assessment of projects in Engineering, providing a reference basis for the comparative analysis of financial and economic indicators. Identifying listed companies that belong to the same sector and industry as the project under study allows, for example, the "opportunity cost of capital" to be determined based on parameters such as the "Beta" factor (CAPM) of the corresponding sector or industry.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data Source

Sector and industry classification data were obtained from the Yahoo Finance platform, which uses a proprietary categorization system. The information was extracted using the yfinance library (version 0.2.51) [1] in a Python 3.11 environment.

2.2 Structuring of Information

The information available on Yahoo Finance covers 11 sectors, equivalent to those defined by the GICS (Global Industry Classification Standard) system [2]. However, unlike GICS, no intermediate classification levels are provided.

In order to bring the structure closer to the GICS model and facilitate educational use, two additional levels have been introduced:

- Sub-sectors (equivalent to GICS industry groups);
- Super-industries (equivalent to GICS industries).

Thus, the classification system used in this document is a "hybrid adaptation" between the Yahoo Finance model and GICS, with the aim of improving the organization and readability of the data.

In addition to the classification system, a practical example of data extraction using the Yahoo Finance API (via the yfinance Python library) is provided in Appendix A. This example illustrates how financial indicators such as Beta, ROA, ROE, and EPS can be obtained for companies within a given industry.

2.3 Adjustments to Yahoo Finance Classification

The sector and industry classification used in this document is primarily based on the taxonomy provided by Yahoo Finance. However, in a few cases, adjustments were made to improve alignment with the Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS). These adjustments reflect differences in the way certain industries are grouped by Yahoo Finance compared to GICS.

The main changes are as follows:

The "Packaging & Containers" industry was moved from "Consumer Cyclical" to "Basic Materials", consistent with the GICS sub-industry "15103010 Metal, Glass & Plastic Containers" under the "Materials" sector.

The "Education & Training Services" industry was moved from "Consumer Defensive" to "Consumer Cyclical", consistent with the GICS sub-industry "25302010 Education Services" under the "Consumer Discretionary" sector.

The "REIT - Mortgage" industry was moved from "Real Estate" to "Financial Services", consistent with the GICS sub-industry "40204010 Mortgage REITs" under the "Financials" sector.

These modifications affect only a small number of industries and do not alter the overall structure of the classification. They were introduced to ensure greater consistency with widely adopted international standards, thus facilitating comparisons across different sources of financial information.

3. Coding System

International classification systems, such as GICS and ICB (Industry Classification Benchmark), use hierarchical numerical codes, where each level adds two digits to the category code.

Example in the GICS system:

```
Sector:          10 Energy
Industry group: 1010 Energy
Industry:        101010 Energy Equipment & Services
Subindustry:    10101010 Oil & Gas Drilling
```

Example in the system adopted in this document:

```
Sector:          10000 Energy
Subsector:       10100 Energy
Super-Industry: 10110 Energy Equipment & Services
Industry:        10111 Oil & Gas Drilling
```

The choice of a fixed five-digit code provides simplicity of reading and hierarchical consistency. In addition, this structure facilitates the integration and filtering of data in analysis tools such as Excel, Python, or relational databases.

4. Classification Structure

This section introduces the full hierarchical system used to classify the securities considered in this study. The taxonomy follows four levels of aggregation (Sector, Subsector, Super-Industry, and Industry), and is presented as an indented tree. For clarity, only the names and codes are shown here, while access to the corresponding definitions is provided in Section 5. This representation allows the reader to quickly identify the relative position of each industry within the broader economic context.

10000 Energy

10100 Energy

- 10110 Energy Equipment & Services
 - 10111 Oil & Gas Drilling
 - 10112 Oil & Gas Equipment & Services
- 10120 Oil Gas & Consumable Fuels
 - 10121 Oil & Gas Integrated
 - 10122 Oil & Gas E&P
 - 10123 Oil & Gas Refining & Marketing
 - 10124 Oil & Gas Midstream
 - 10125 Thermal Coal
 - 10126 Uranium

15000 Basic Materials

15100 Basic Materials

- 15110 Chemicals
 - 15111 Chemicals
 - 15112 Agricultural Inputs
 - 15113 Specialty Chemicals
- 15120 Construction Materials
 - 15121 Building Materials
- 15130 Packaging & Containers
 - 15131 Packaging & Containers
- 15140 Metals & Mining
 - 15141 Aluminum
 - 15142 Other Industrial Metals & Mining
 - 15143 Copper
 - 15144 Gold
 - 15145 Other Precious Metals & Mining
 - 15146 Silver
 - 15147 Steel
 - 15148 Coking Coal
- 15150 Paper & Forest Products
 - 15151 Lumber & Wood Production
 - 15152 Paper & Paper Products

20000 Industrials

20100 Capital Goods

- 20110 Aerospace & Defense
 - 20111 Aerospace & Defense
- 20120 Building Products & Equipment
 - 20121 Building Products & Equipment
- 20130 Engineering & Construction

- 20131 Engineering & Construction
- 20132 Metal Fabrication
- 20140 Electrical Equipment
 - 20141 Electrical Equipment & Parts
 - 20142 Tools & Accessories
- 20150 Industrial Conglomerates
 - 20151 Conglomerates
- 20160 Machinery
 - 20161 Farm & Heavy Construction Machinery
 - 20162 Specialty Industrial Machinery
- 20170 Industrial Distribution
 - 20171 Industrial Distribution
- 20200 Commercial & Professional Services**
 - 20210 Commercial Services & Supplies
 - 20211 Waste Management
 - 20212 Pollution & Treatment Controls
 - 20213 Business Equipment & Supplies
 - 20214 Security & Protection Services
 - 20215 Rental & Leasing Services
 - 20220 Professional Services
 - 20221 Staffing & Employment Services
 - 20222 Consulting Services
 - 20223 Specialty Business Services
- 20300 Transportation**
 - 20310 Air Freight & Logistics
 - 20311 Integrated Freight & Logistics
 - 20320 Passenger Airlines
 - 20321 Airlines
 - 20330 Marine Transportation
 - 20331 Marine Shipping
 - 20340 Ground Transportation
 - 20341 Railroads
 - 20342 Trucking
 - 20350 Transportation Infrastructure
 - 20351 Airports & Air Services
- 25000 Consumer Cyclical**
 - 25100 Automobiles & Components
 - 25110 Automobile Components
 - 25111 Auto Parts
 - 25120 Automobiles
 - 25121 Auto Manufacturers
 - 25200 Consumer Cyclical & Apparel
 - 25210 Household Durables
 - 25211 Residential Construction
 - 25220 Leisure Products
 - 25221 Leisure
 - 25222 Recreational Vehicles
 - 25230 Textiles Apparel & Luxury Goods
 - 25231 Luxury Goods
 - 25232 Apparel Manufacturing
 - 25233 Footwear & Accessories
 - 25234 Textile Manufacturing

25300 Consumer Cyclical Services

25310 Hotels Restaurants & Leisure

25311 Gambling

25312 Resorts & Casinos

25313 Travel Services

25314 Lodging

25315 Restaurants

25320 Diversified Consumer Services

25321 Education & Training Services

25322 Personal Services

25400 Consumer Cyclical Distribution & Retail

25410 Internet Retail

25411 Internet Retail

25420 Broadline Retail

25421 Department Stores

25430 Specialty Retail

25431 Apparel Retail

25432 Home Improvement Retail

25433 Specialty Retail

25434 Auto & Truck Dealerships

25435 Furnishings Fixtures & Appliances

30000 Consumer Defensive

30100 Consumer Defensive Distribution & Retail

30110 Consumer Defensive Distribution & Retail

30111 Food Distribution

30112 Grocery Stores

30113 Discount Stores

30200 Food Beverage & Tobacco

30210 Beverages

30211 Beverages-Brewers

30212 Beverages-Wineries & Distilleries

30213 Beverages-Non-Alcoholic

30220 Food Products

30221 Farm Products

30222 Packaged Foods

30223 Confectioners

30230 Tobacco

30231 Tobacco

30300 Household & Personal Products

30310 Household & Personal Products

30311 Household & Personal Products

35000 Healthcare

35100 Healthcare Equipment & Services

35110 Healthcare Equipment & Supplies

35111 Medical Devices

35112 Medical Instruments & Supplies

35120 Healthcare Providers & Services

35121 Medical Distribution

35122 Pharmaceutical Retailers

35123 Diagnostics & Research

35124 Medical Care Facilities

35125 Healthcare Plans

- 35130 Healthcare Technology
 - 35131 Health Information Services
- 35200 Pharmaceuticals & Biotechnology
 - 35210 Biotechnology
 - 35211 Biotechnology
 - 35220 Pharmaceuticals
 - 35221 Drug Manufacturers-General
 - 35222 Drug Manufacturers-Specialty & Generic

40000 Financial Services

- 40100 Banks
 - 40110 Banks
 - 40111 Banks-Diversified
 - 40112 Banks-Regional
- 40200 Financial Services
 - 40210 Financial Services
 - 40211 Financial Conglomerates
 - 40212 Mortgage Finance
 - 40213 Shell Companies
 - 40220 Consumer Finance
 - 40221 Credit Services
 - 40230 Capital Markets
 - 40231 Asset Management
 - 40232 Capital Markets
 - 40233 Financial Data & Stock Exchanges
 - 40240 Mortgage REITs
 - 40241 REIT-Mortgage
- 40300 Insurance
 - 40310 Insurance
 - 40311 Insurance Brokers
 - 40312 Insurance-Life
 - 40313 Insurance-Diversified
 - 40314 Insurance-Specialty
 - 40315 Insurance-Property & Casualty
 - 40316 Insurance-Reinsurance

45000 Technology

- 45100 Software & Services
 - 45110 Information Technology Services
 - 45111 Information Technology Services
 - 45120 Software
 - 45121 Software-Application
 - 45122 Software-Infrastructure
- 45200 Technology Hardware & Equipment
 - 45210 Communications Equipment
 - 45211 Communication Equipment
 - 45220 Computer Hardware
 - 45221 Computer Hardware
 - 45230 Electronic Equipment Instruments & Components
 - 45231 Consumer Electronics
 - 45232 Electronic Components
 - 45233 Scientific & Technical Instruments
 - 45234 Electronics & Computer Distribution

45300 Semiconductors & Semiconductor Equipment

- 45310 Semiconductors & Semiconductor Equipment
 - 45311 Semiconductor Equipment & Materials
 - 45312 Semiconductors
 - 45313 Solar

50000 Communication Services

- 50100 Telecommunication Services
 - 50110 Telecommunication Services
 - 50111 Telecom Services
- 50200 Media & Entertainment
 - 50210 Media
 - 50211 Advertising Agencies
 - 50212 Broadcasting
 - 50213 Publishing
 - 50220 Entertainment
 - 50221 Entertainment
 - 50222 Electronic Gaming & Multimedia
 - 50230 Internet Content & Information
 - 50231 Internet Content & Information

55000 Utilities

- 55100 Utilities
 - 55110 Electric Utilities
 - 55111 Utilities-Regulated Electric
 - 55120 Gas Utilities
 - 55121 Utilities-Regulated Gas
 - 55130 Diversified Utilities
 - 55131 Utilities-Diversified
 - 55140 Water Utilities
 - 55141 Utilities-Regulated Water
 - 55150 Electricity Independent Power Producers
 - 55151 Utilities-Independent Power Producers
 - 55152 Utilities-Renewable

60000 Real Estate

- 60100 Equity Real Estate Investment Trusts
 - 60110 Diversified REITs
 - 60111 REIT-Diversified
 - 60120 Industrial REITs
 - 60121 REIT-Industrial
 - 60130 Hotel & Resort REITs
 - 60131 REIT-Hotel & Motel
 - 60140 Office REITs
 - 60141 REIT-Office
 - 60150 Health Care REITs
 - 60151 REIT-Healthcare Facilities
 - 60160 Residential REITs
 - 60161 REIT-Residential
 - 60170 Retail REITs
 - 60171 REIT-Retail
 - 60180 Specialized REITs
 - 60181 REIT-Specialty

- 60200 Real Estate Management & Development
 - 60210 Real Estate Management & Development
 - 60211 Real Estate-Diversified
 - 60212 Real Estate-Development
 - 60213 Real Estate Services

5. Sector and Industry Definitions

This dataset classifies companies according to the sector and industry taxonomy used by Yahoo Finance. To ensure clarity and access to the most accurate information, the names of each sector and industry listed below are direct links to their official definitions on the Yahoo Finance website.

This method provides a direct reference to the primary source, allowing users to understand the scope and characteristics of each category as defined by the data provider.

[10000 Energy](#)

- [10111 Oil & Gas Drilling](#)
- [10112 Oil & Gas Equipment & Services](#)
- [10121 Oil & Gas Integrated](#)
- [10122 Oil & Gas E&P](#)
- [10123 Oil & Gas Refining & Marketing](#)
- [10124 Oil & Gas Midstream](#)
- [10125 Thermal Coal](#)
- [10126 Uranium](#)

[15000 Basic Materials](#)

- [15111 Chemicals](#)
- [15112 Agricultural Inputs](#)
- [15113 Specialty Chemicals](#)
- [15121 Building Materials](#)
- [15131 Packaging & Containers](#)
- [15141 Aluminum](#)
- [15142 Other Industrial Metals & Mining](#)
- [15143 Copper](#)
- [15144 Gold](#)
- [15145 Other Precious Metals & Mining](#)
- [15146 Silver](#)
- [15147 Steel](#)
- [15148 Coking Coal](#)
- [15151 Lumber & Wood Production](#)
- [15152 Paper & Paper Products](#)

[20000 Industrials](#)

- [20111 Aerospace & Defense](#)
- [20121 Building Products & Equipment](#)
- [20131 Engineering & Construction](#)
- [20132 Metal Fabrication](#)
- [20141 Electrical Equipment & Parts](#)
- [20142 Tools & Accessories](#)
- [20151 Conglomerates](#)
- [20161 Farm & Heavy Construction Machinery](#)

[20162 Specialty Industrial Machinery](#)
[20171 Industrial Distribution](#)
[20211 Waste Management](#)
[20212 Pollution & Treatment Controls](#)
[20213 Business Equipment & Supplies](#)
[20214 Security & Protection Services](#)
[20215 Rental & Leasing Services](#)
[20221 Staffing & Employment Services](#)
[20222 Consulting Services](#)
[20223 Specialty Business Services](#)
[20311 Integrated Freight & Logistics](#)
[20321 Airlines](#)
[20331 Marine Shipping](#)
[20341 Railroads](#)
[20342 Trucking](#)
[20351 Airports & Air Services](#)

[25000 Consumer Cyclical](#)

[25111 Auto Parts](#)
[25121 Auto Manufacturers](#)
[25211 Residential Construction](#)
[25221 Leisure](#)
[25222 Recreational Vehicles](#)
[25231 Luxury Goods](#)
[25232 Apparel Manufacturing](#)
[25233 Footwear & Accessories](#)
[25234 Textile Manufacturing](#)
[25311 Gambling](#)
[25312 Resorts & Casinos](#)
[25313 Travel Services](#)
[25314 Lodging](#)
[25315 Restaurants](#)
[25321 Education & Training Services](#)
[25322 Personal Services](#)
[25411 Internet Retail](#)
[25421 Department Stores](#)
[25431 Apparel Retail](#)
[25432 Home Improvement Retail](#)
[25433 Specialty Retail](#)
[25434 Auto & Truck Dealerships](#)
[25435 Furnishings Fixtures & Appliances](#)

[30000 Consumer Defensive](#)

[30111 Food Distribution](#)
[30112 Grocery Stores](#)
[30113 Discount Stores](#)
[30211 Beverages-Brewers](#)
[30212 Beverages-Wineries & Distilleries](#)
[30213 Beverages-Non-Alcoholic](#)
[30221 Farm Products](#)
[30222 Packaged Foods](#)
[30223 Confectioners](#)
[30231 Tobacco](#)
[30311 Household & Personal Products](#)

35000 Healthcare

- 35111 Medical Devices
- 35112 Medical Instruments & Supplies
- 35121 Medical Distribution
- 35122 Pharmaceutical Retailers
- 35123 Diagnostics & Research
- 35124 Medical Care Facilities
- 35125 Healthcare Plans
- 35131 Health Information Services
- 35211 Biotechnology
- 35221 Drug Manufacturers-General
- 35222 Drug Manufacturers-Specialty & Generic

40000 Financial Services

- 40111 Banks-Diversified
- 40112 Banks-Regional
- 40211 Financial Conglomerates
- 40212 Mortgage Finance
- 40213 Shell Companies
- 40221 Credit Services
- 40231 Asset Management
- 40232 Capital Markets
- 40233 Financial Data & Stock Exchanges
- 40241 REIT-Mortgage
- 40311 Insurance Brokers
- 40312 Insurance-Life
- 40313 Insurance-Diversified
- 40314 Insurance-Specialty
- 40315 Insurance-Property & Casualty
- 40316 Insurance-Reinsurance

45000 Technology

- 45111 Information Technology Services
- 45121 Software-Application
- 45122 Software-Infrastructure
- 45211 Communication Equipment
- 45221 Computer Hardware
- 45231 Consumer Electronics
- 45232 Electronic Components
- 45233 Scientific & Technical Instruments
- 45234 Electronics & Computer Distribution
- 45311 Semiconductor Equipment & Materials
- 45312 Semiconductors
- 45313 Solar

50000 Communication Services

- 50111 Telecom Services
- 50211 Advertising Agencies
- 50212 Broadcasting
- 50213 Publishing
- 50221 Entertainment
- 50222 Electronic Gaming & Multimedia
- 50231 Internet Content & Information

55000 Utilities

55111 Utilities-Regulated Electric

55121 Utilities-Regulated Gas

55131 Utilities-Diversified

55141 Utilities-Regulated Water

55151 Utilities-Independent Power Producers

55152 Utilities-Renewable

60000 Real Estate

60111 REIT-Diversified

60121 REIT-Industrial

60131 REIT-Hotel & Motel

60141 REIT-Office

60151 REIT-Healthcare Facilities

60161 REIT-Residential

60171 REIT-Retail

60181 REIT-Specialty

60211 Real Estate-Diversified

60212 Real Estate-Development

60213 Real Estate Services

6. Limitations

Yahoo Finance's classification is proprietary and does not fully comply with international standards, and may differ from GICS or ICB. The data reflects the state of the market as of September 28, 2025, and therefore needs to be updated periodically to remain relevant. Despite the introduction of intermediate classification levels, the proposed structure is an "educational adaptation" and does not correspond exactly to the official systems.

7. References

[1] Ran, A. (2024). Yfinance (version 0.2.51). Available at: <https://github.com/ranaroussi/yfinance>

[2] MSCI & S&P Dow Jones Indices (2024). Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS) Methodology. Available at: <https://www.msci.com/our-solutions/indexes/gics>

Appendix A. Python Example: Extracting Financial Indicators from Yahoo Finance

This appendix provides a practical example of how to retrieve selected financial indicators for publicly traded companies using the yfinance Python library. The aim is to illustrate how students and researchers can directly access updated financial data from Yahoo Finance to complement project valuation exercises.

The example focuses on the industry "20132: Metal Fabrication" of sector "20000: Industrials", for which the dataset includes eleven companies. The script demonstrates how to extract the following indicators: Beta, Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings per Share (EPS).

The extracted data are first stored in a "pandas DataFrame" and subsequently exported to an "Excel file" (metal fabrication.xlsx). For clarity, a preview of the resulting table is also included below.

Python Script

```
import yfinance as yf
import pandas as pd

# List of tickers for industry "20132: Metal Fabrication"
tickers = ['BEKB.BR', 'NDA.DE', 'SIFG.AS', 'ATI', 'CMPO', 'CRS', 'ESAB',
           'IIIN', 'MLI', 'PRLB', 'WOR']

# Collect data
data = []
for ticker in tickers:
    # Try to download data for ticker
    try:
        stock = yf.Ticker(ticker)
        info = stock.get_info()
        if len(info) < 10:
            raise ValueError("no data found")
        print(f"Getting data for stock {ticker}")
        data.append({
            "Ticker": ticker,
            "Name": info.get("longName", ""),
            "Beta": info.get("beta", None),
            "ROA": info.get("returnOnAssets", None),
            "ROE": info.get("returnOnEquity", None),
            "EPS": info.get("trailingEps", None)
        })
    # Ignore errors and continue
    except Exception as e:
        print(f"> Stock {ticker} ignored: {e}")

# Convert to DataFrame and save to Excel
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
print(df)
output file = "metal fabrication.xlsx"
df.to_excel(output file, index=False)
```

Example of Output Table

Ticker	Name	Beta	ROA	ROE	EPS
BEKB.BR	NV Bekaert SA	1.443	0.0491	0.0815	3.32
NDA.DE	Aurubis AG	1.097	0.0598	0.1307	14.12
SIFG.AS	Sif Holding N.V.	0.700	-0.0324	-0.1392	-1.14
ATI	ATI Inc.	1.269	0.0761	0.2605	2.90
CMPO	CompoSecure, Inc.	0.995	0.1133	NaN	-2.01
CRS	Carpenter Technology Corporat	1.530	0.0940	0.2139	7.41
ESAB	ESAB Corporation	1.218	0.0674	0.1487	4.65
IIIN	Insteel Industries, Inc.	0.722	0.0569	0.0887	1.59
MLI	Mueller Industries, Inc.	1.053	0.1597	0.2612	6.29
PRLB	Proto Labs, Inc.	1.269	0.0186	0.0219	0.60
WOR	Worthington Enterprises, Inc.	1.110	0.0243	0.1136	0.22

Appendix B. List of Companies by Sector and Industry

10000 Energy

10100 Energy

10110 Energy Equipment & Services

10111 Oil & Gas Drilling

1. HP Helmerich & Payne Inc
2. NBR Nabors Industries Ltd
3. NE Noble Corp PLC
4. PTEN Patterson-UTI Energy Inc
5. SDRL Seadrill Ltd
6. SOC Sable Offshore Corp

10112 Oil & Gas Equipment & Services

1. EXM.BR Exmar NV
2. FUR.AS Fugro NV
3. GTT.PA Gaztransport & Technigaz SA
4. SBMO.AS SBM Offshore NV
5. TE.PA Technip Energies NV
6. ACDC ProFrac Holding Corp
7. AESI Atlas Energy Solutions Inc
8. AROC Archrock Inc
9. BKR Baker Hughes Co
10. CLB Core Laboratories Inc
11. FTI TechnipFMC PLC
12. HAL Halliburton Co
13. HLX Helix Energy Solutions Group Inc
14. INVX Innovex International Inc
15. KGS Kodiak Gas Services Inc
16. LBRT Liberty Energy Inc
17. NEXT NextDecade Corp
18. NOV NOV Inc
19. OII Oceaneering International Inc
20. PUMP ProPetro Holding Corp
21. RES RPC Inc
22. SLB Schlumberger Ltd
23. SND Smart Sand Inc
24. TDW Tidewater Inc
25. VAL Valaris Ltd
26. VTOL Bristow Group Inc
27. WFRD Weatherford International PLC
28. WHD Cactus Inc

10120 Oil Gas & Consumable Fuels

10121 Oil & Gas Integrated

1. GALP.LS Galp Energia SGPS
2. SHELL.AS Shell plc
3. TTE.PA TotalEnergies SE
4. CRGY Crescent Energy Co
5. CVX Chevron Corp
6. NFG National Fuel Gas Co

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

7.	XOM	Exxon Mobil Corp
10122	Oil & Gas E&P	
1.	MAU.PA	Etablissements Maurel & Prom SA
2.	APA	APA Corp
3.	AR	Antero Resources Corp
4.	CHRD	Chord Energy Corp
5.	CIVI	Civitas Resources Inc
6.	CNX	CNX Resources Corp
7.	COP	ConocoPhillips
8.	CRC	California Resources Corp
9.	CRK	Comstock Resources Inc
10.	CTRA	Coterra Energy Inc
11.	DMLP	Dorchester Minerals LP
12.	DVN	Devon Energy Corp
13.	EOG	EOG Resources Inc
14.	EQT	EQT Corp
15.	EXE	Expand Energy Corp
16.	FANG	Diamondback Energy Inc
17.	HPK	HighPeak Energy Inc
18.	MGY	Magnolia Oil & Gas Corp
19.	MTDR	Matador Resources Co
20.	MUR	Murphy Oil Corp
21.	NOG	Northern Oil and Gas Inc
22.	OVV	Ovintiv Inc
23.	OXY	Occidental Petroleum Corp
24.	PR	Permian Resources Corp
25.	RRC	Range Resources Corp
26.	SM	SM Energy Co
27.	TALO	Talos Energy Inc
28.	TPL	Texas Pacific Land Corp
29.	VTLE	Vital Energy Inc
10123	Oil & Gas Refining & Marketing	
1.	RUI.PA	Rubis
2.	CVI	CVR Energy Inc
3.	DINO	HF Sinclair Corp
4.	IEP	Icahn Enterprises LP
5.	MPC	Marathon Petroleum Corp
6.	PARR	Par Pacific Holdings Inc
7.	PBF	PBF Energy Inc
8.	PSX	Phillips 66
9.	VLO	Valero Energy Corp
10.	WKC	World Kinect Corp
10124	Oil & Gas Midstream	
1.	VPK.AS	Koninklijke Vopak NV
2.	AM	Antero Midstream Corp
3.	DTM	DT Midstream Inc
4.	EPD	Enterprise Products Partners LP
5.	ET	Energy Transfer LP
6.	GLNG	Golar LNG Ltd
7.	INSW	International Seaways Inc
8.	KMI	Kinder Morgan Inc
9.	KNTK	Kinetik Holdings Inc

10.	LNG	Cheniere Energy Inc
11.	LPG	Dorian LPG Ltd
12.	NFE	New Fortress Energy Inc
13.	OKE	ONEOK Inc
14.	PAA	Plains All American Pipeline LP
15.	PAGP	Plains GP Holdings LP
16.	TRGP	Targa Resources Corp
17.	TRMD	TORM PLC
18.	VNOM	Viper Energy Inc
19.	WMB	The Williams Companies Inc
10125 Thermal Coal		
1.	ARLP	Alliance Resource Partners LP
2.	BTU	Peabody Energy Corp
3.	CNR	Core Natural Resources Inc
4.	HNRG	Hallador Energy Co
5.	NC	NACCO Industries Inc
6.	NRP	Natural Resource Partners LP
10126 Uranium		
1.	LEU	Centrus Energy Corp
2.	UEC	Uranium Energy Corp

15000 Basic Materials

15100 Basic Materials

15110 Chemicals

15111 Chemicals		
1.	BAS.DE	BASF SE
2.	SGL.DE	SGL Carbon SE
3.	SOLB.BR	Solvay SA
4.	SYENS.BR	Syensqo SA
5.	ASIX	AdvanSix Inc
6.	CE	Celanese Corp
7.	DOW	Dow Inc
8.	HUN	Huntsman Corp
9.	MEOH	Methanex Corp
10.	OLN	Olin Corp
11.	REX	REX American Resources Corp
15112 Agricultural Inputs		
1.	SDF.DE	K+S AG
2.	TESB.BR	Tessenderlo Group NV
3.	CF	CF Industries Holdings Inc
4.	CTVA	Corteva Inc
5.	FMC	FMC Corp
6.	MOS	The Mosaic Co
7.	SMG	The Scotts Miracle-Gro Co
15113 Specialty Chemicals		
1.	1COV.DE	Covestro AG
2.	AI.PA	L'Air Liquide SA
3.	AKE.PA	Arkema SA
4.	AKZA.AS	Akzo Nobel NV
5.	AVTX.AS	Avantium NV

6.	AZE.BR	Azelis Group NV
7.	BNR.DE	Brenntag SE
8.	CRBN.AS	Corbion NV
9.	DSFIR.AS	DSM-Firmenich AG
10.	EVK.DE	Evonik Industries AG
11.	FPE3.DE	Fuchs SE
12.	IMCD.AS	IMCD NV
13.	LIN.DE	Linde PLC
14.	LXS.DE	LANXESS AG
15.	OCI.AS	OCI NV
16.	SY1.DE	Symrise AG
17.	WCH.DE	Wacker Chemie AG
18.	ALB	Albemarle Corp
19.	ALTO	Alto Ingredients Inc
20.	APD	Air Products and Chemicals Inc
21.	ASH	Ashland Inc
22.	AVNT	Avient Corp
23.	AXTA	Axalta Coating Systems Ltd
24.	BCPC	Balchem Corp
25.	CBT	Cabot Corp
26.	CC	The Chemours Co
27.	CLMT	Calumet Inc
28.	DD	DuPont de Nemours Inc
29.	ECL	Ecolab Inc
30.	EMN	Eastman Chemical Co
31.	ESI	Element Solutions Inc
32.	FUL	HB Fuller Co
33.	HWKN	Hawkins Inc
34.	IFF	International Flavors & Fragrances Inc
35.	IOSP	Innospec Inc
36.	KOP	Koppers Holdings Inc
37.	KWR	Quaker Chemical Corp
38.	LWLG	Lightwave Logic Inc
39.	LYB	LyondellBasell Industries NV
40.	MNTK	Montauk Renewables Inc
41.	MTX	Minerals Technologies Inc
42.	NEU	NewMarket Corp
43.	NGVT	Ingevity Corp
44.	PPG	PPG Industries Inc
45.	RPM	RPM International Inc
46.	SCL	Stepan Co
47.	SHW	The Sherwin-Williams Co
48.	SXT	Sensient Technologies Corp
49.	WDFC	WD-40 Co
50.	WLK	Westlake Corp

15120 Construction Materials

15121 Building Materials

1.	HEI.DE	Heidelberg Materials AG
2.	CRH	CRH PLC
3.	EXP	Eagle Materials Inc
4.	JHX	James Hardie Industries PLC
5.	KNF	Knife River Corp
6.	MLM	Martin Marietta Materials Inc

- 7. USLM United States Lime & Minerals Inc
- 8. VMC Vulcan Materials Co

15130 Packaging & Containers

- 15131 Packaging & Containers
 - 1. AMCR Amcor PLC
 - 2. AVY Avery Dennison Corp
 - 3. BALL Ball Corp
 - 4. CCK Crown Holdings Inc
 - 5. GEF Greif Inc
 - 6. GPK Graphic Packaging Holding Co
 - 7. IP International Paper Co
 - 8. OI O-I Glass Inc
 - 9. PKG Packaging Corp of America
 - 10. REYN Reynolds Consumer Products Inc
 - 11. SEE Sealed Air Corp
 - 12. SLGN Silgan Holdings Inc
 - 13. SON Sonoco Products Co
 - 14. SW Smurfit Westrock PLC
 - 15. TRS TriMas Corp

15140 Metals & Mining

- 15141 Aluminum
 - 1. AA Alcoa Corp
 - 2. CENX Century Aluminum Co
 - 3. KALU Kaiser Aluminum Corp
- 15142 Other Industrial Metals & Mining
 - 1. AMG.AS AMG Critical Materials NV
 - 2. ERA.PA ERAMET SA
 - 3. NYR.BR Nyrstar NV
 - 4. GSM Ferroglobe PLC
 - 5. MP MP Materials Corp
 - 6. MTRN Materion Corp
 - 7. TMC TMC the metals company Inc
 - 8. USAR USA Rare Earth Inc
- 15143 Copper
 - 1. FCX Freeport-McMoRan Inc
 - 2. IE Ivanhoe Electric Inc
 - 3. MTAL MAC Copper Ltd
 - 4. SCCO Southern Copper Corp
- 15144 Gold
 - 1. ALAMG.PA Auplata Mining Group
 - 2. AU AngloGold Ashanti PLC
 - 3. AUGO Aura Minerals Inc
 - 4. B Barrick Mining Corp
 - 5. BGL Blue Gold Ltd
 - 6. NAMM Namib Minerals
 - 7. NEM Newmont Corp
 - 8. RGLD Royal Gold Inc
 - 9. SSRM SSR Mining Inc
- 15145 Other Precious Metals & Mining
 - 1. HL Hecla Mining Co

- 2. MUX McEwen Inc
- 3. PPTA Perpetua Resources Corp
- 15146 Silver
 - 1. EXK Endeavour Silver Corp
- 15147 Steel
 - 1. APAM.AS Aperam SA
 - 2. KCO.DE Klöckner & Co SE
 - 3. MT.AS ArcelorMittal SA
 - 4. RAM.LS Ramada Investimentos e Industria SA
 - 5. SZG.DE Salzgitter AG
 - 6. VK.PA Vallourec SA
 - 7. ASTL Algoma Steel Group Inc
 - 8. CLF Cleveland-Cliffs Inc
 - 9. CMC Commercial Metals Co
 - 10. MTUS Metallus Inc
 - 11. NUE Nucor Corp
 - 12. RS Reliance Inc
 - 13. STLD Steel Dynamics Inc
 - 14. WS Worthington Steel Inc
- 15148 Coking Coal
 - 1. AMR Alpha Metallurgical Resources Inc
 - 2. HCC Warrior Met Coal Inc
 - 3. METC Ramaco Resources Inc
 - 4. SXC SunCoke Energy Inc

15150 Paper & Forest Products

- 15151 Lumber & Wood Production
 - 1. COR.LS Corticeira Amorim SGPS
 - 2. BCC Boise Cascade Co
 - 3. SSD Simpson Manufacturing Co Inc
 - 4. UFPI UFP Industries Inc
- 15152 Paper & Paper Products
 - 1. ALTR.LS Altri SGPS
 - 2. NVG.LS The Navigator Company SA
 - 3. SEM.LS Semapa SGPS
 - 4. CLW Clearwater Paper Corp
 - 5. MAGN Magnera Corp
 - 6. SLVM Sylvamo Corp

20000 Industrials

20100 Capital Goods

20110 Aerospace & Defense

- 20111 Aerospace & Defense
 - 1. AIR.PA Airbus SE
 - 2. AM.PA Dassault Aviation SA
 - 3. HAG.DE Hensoldt AG
 - 4. HO.PA Thales SA
 - 5. MTX.DE MTU Aero Engines AG
 - 6. RHM.DE Rheinmetall AG
 - 7. SAF.PA Safran SA

8.	AIR	AAR Corp
9.	ATRO	Astronics Corp
10.	AVAV	AeroVironment Inc
11.	AXON	Axon Enterprise Inc
12.	BA	The Boeing Co
13.	BWXT	BWX Technologies Inc
14.	CW	Curtiss-Wright Corp
15.	DRS	Leonardo DRS Inc
16.	ESLT	Elbit Systems Ltd
17.	FLY	Firefly Aerospace Inc
18.	GD	General Dynamics Corp
19.	GE	GE Aerospace
20.	HEI	HEICO Corp
21.	HEI-A	HEICO Corp
22.	HII	Huntington Ingalls Industries Inc
23.	HWM	Howmet Aerospace Inc
24.	HXL	Hexcel Corp
25.	KRMN	Karman Holdings Inc
26.	KTOS	Kratos Defense & Security Solutions Inc
27.	LHX	L3Harris Technologies Inc
28.	LILMF	Lilium NV
29.	LMT	Lockheed Martin Corp
30.	LOAR	Loar Holdings Inc
31.	LUNR	Intuitive Machines Inc
32.	MOG-A	Moog Inc
33.	MRCY	Mercury Systems Inc
34.	NOC	Northrop Grumman Corp
35.	NPK	National Presto Industries Inc
36.	RGR	Sturm Ruger & Co Inc
37.	RKLB	Rocket Lab Corp
38.	RTX	RTX Corp
39.	SARO	StandardAero Inc
40.	SPR	Spirit AeroSystems Holdings Inc
41.	TDG	TransDigm Group Inc
42.	TXT	Textron Inc
43.	VSEC	VSE Corp
44.	WWD	Woodward Inc

20120 Building Products & Equipment

20121	Building Products & Equipment	
1.	SGO.PA	Compagnie de Saint-Gobain SA
2.	AAON	AAON Inc
3.	APOG	Apogee Enterprises Inc
4.	ARLO	Arlo Technologies Inc
5.	AWI	Armstrong World Industries Inc
6.	BLDR	Builders FirstSource Inc
7.	CARR	Carrier Global Corp
8.	CSL	Carlisle Companies Inc
9.	FBIN	Fortune Brands Innovations Inc
10.	GFF	Griffon Corp
11.	GMS	GMS Inc
12.	JCI	Johnson Controls International PLC
13.	LII	Lennox International Inc
14.	LMB	Limbach Holdings Inc

15. LPX Louisiana-Pacific Corp
16. MAS Masco Corp
17. NX Quanex Building Products Corp
18. OC Owens Corning
19. ROCK Gibraltar Industries Inc
20. SPXC SPX Technologies Inc
21. TREX Trex Co Inc
22. TT Trane Technologies PLC
23. WMS Advanced Drainage Systems Inc

20130 Engineering & Construction

20131 Engineering & Construction

1. ACKB.BR Ackermans & Van Haaren NV
2. ARCAD.AS Arcadis NV
3. ASY.PA Assystem SA
4. BAMNB.AS Koninklijke BAM Groep nv
5. DG.PA Vinci SA
6. EGL.LS Mota Engil SGPS
7. EN.PA Bouygues SA
8. FGR.PA Eiffage SA
9. GBF.DE Bilfinger SE
10. HEIJM.AS Koninklijke Heijmans NV
11. HOT.DE HOCHTIEF AG
12. MAR.LS Martifer SGPS
13. SPIE.PA SPIE SA
14. TDSA.LS Teixeira Duarte SA
15. ACA Arcosa Inc
16. ACM AECOM
17. APG APi Group Corp
18. BLD TopBuild Corp
19. DY Dycom Industries Inc
20. ECG Everus Construction Group Inc
21. EME EMCOR Group Inc
22. EXPO Exponent Inc
23. FER Ferrovial SE
24. FIX Comfort Systems USA Inc
25. FLR Fluor Corp
26. GLDD Great Lakes Dredge & Dock Corp
27. GVA Granite Construction Inc
28. IESC IES Holdings Inc
29. J Jacobs Solutions Inc
30. KBR KBR Inc
31. MTZ MasTec Inc
32. MYRG MYR Group Inc
33. NVEE NV5 Global Inc
34. PWR Quanta Services Inc
35. ROAD Construction Partners Inc
36. STRL Sterling Infrastructure Inc
37. TTEK Tetra Tech Inc
38. WLDN Willdan Group Inc

20132 Metal Fabrication

1. BEKB.BR NV Bekaert SA
2. NDA.DE Aurubis AG

3. SIFG.AS Sif Holding NV
4. ATI ATI Inc
5. CMPO CompoSecure Inc
6. CRS Carpenter Technology Corp
7. ESAB ESAB Corp
8. IIIN Insteel Industries Inc
9. MLI Mueller Industries Inc
10. PRLB Proto Labs Inc
11. WOR Worthington Enterprises Inc

20140 Electrical Equipment

20141 Electrical Equipment & Parts

1. ALFEN.AS Alfen NV
2. LR.PA Legrand SA
3. MRN.PA Mersen SA
4. NEX.PA Nexans SA
5. OSR.HM OSRAM Licht AG
6. AEIS Advanced Energy Industries Inc
7. AYI Acuity Inc
8. ENR Energizer Holdings Inc
9. ENS EnerSys
10. ENVX Enovix Corp
11. EOSE Eos Energy Enterprises Inc
12. HAYW Hayward Holdings Inc
13. HUBB Hubbell Inc
14. NVT nVent Electric PLC
15. PLUG Plug Power Inc
16. POWL Powell Industries Inc
17. VRT Vertiv Holdings Co

20142 Tools & Accessories

1. HLMN Hillman Solutions Corp
2. KMT Kennametal Inc
3. LECO Lincoln Electric Holdings Inc
4. RBC RBC Bearings Inc
5. SNA Snap-on Inc
6. SWK Stanley Black & Decker Inc
7. TKR The Timken Co
8. TTC The Toro Co

20150 Industrial Conglomerates

20151 Conglomerates

1. TKA.DE thyssenkrupp AG
2. DLX Deluxe Corp
3. HON Honeywell International Inc
4. MATW Matthews International Corp
5. MMM 3M Co
6. NNBR NN Inc
7. OTTR Otter Tail Corp
8. SEB Seaboard Corp
9. VMI Valmont Industries Inc

20160 Machinery

20161 Farm & Heavy Construction Machinery

1. 8TRA.DE Traton SE

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

2.	DTG.DE	Daimler Truck Holding AG
3.	EXO.AS	Exor NV
4.	KGX.DE	KION GROUP AG
5.	WAC.DE	Wacker Neuson SE
6.	AGCO	AGCO Corp
7.	ALG	Alamo Group Inc
8.	ASTE	Astec Industries Inc
9.	BLBD	Blue Bird Corp
10.	CAT	Caterpillar Inc
11.	CMCO	Columbus McKinnon Corp
12.	CNH	CNH Industrial NV
13.	DE	Deere & Co
14.	LNN	Lindsay Corp
15.	OSK	Oshkosh Corp
16.	PCAR	PACCAR Inc
17.	TEX	Terex Corp
18.	TWI	Titan International Inc
20162		Specialty Industrial Machinery
1.	AALB.AS	Aalberts NV
2.	AGFB.BR	Agfa-Gevaert NV
3.	ENR.DE	Siemens Energy AG
4.	G1A.DE	GEA Group AG
5.	HDD.DE	Heidelberger Druckmaschinen AG
6.	JUN3.DE	Jungheinrich AG
7.	KENDR.AS	Kendrion NV
8.	KRN.DE	Krones AG
9.	MLAAT.PA	Azorean Aquatic Technologies SA
10.	NDX1.DE	Nordex SE
11.	RAA.DE	RATIONAL AG
12.	SIE.DE	Siemens AG
13.	SKB.DE	Koenig & Bauer AG
14.	STM.DE	Stabilus SE
15.	SU.PA	Schneider Electric SE
16.	AME	AMETEK Inc
17.	AMSC	American Superconductor Corp
18.	AOS	A O Smith Corp
19.	CMI	Cummins Inc
20.	CR	Crane Co
21.	CSW	CSW Industrials Inc
22.	CXT	Crane NXT Co
23.	DCI	Donaldson Co Inc
24.	DOV	Dover Corp
25.	EMR	Emerson Electric Co
26.	EPAC	Enerpac Tool Group Corp
27.	ETN	Eaton Corp PLC
28.	FELE	Franklin Electric Co Inc
29.	FLS	Flowserve Corp
30.	GEV	GE Vernova Inc
31.	GGG	Graco Inc
32.	GNRC	Generac Holdings Inc
33.	GTES	Gates Industrial Corp PLC
34.	GTLS	Chart Industries Inc
35.	HI	Hillenbrand Inc

36.	IEX	IDEX Corp
37.	IR	Ingersoll Rand Inc
38.	ITT	ITT Inc
39.	ITW	Illinois Tool Works Inc
40.	JBTM	JBT Marel Corp
41.	KAI	Kadant Inc
42.	KRNT	Kornit Digital Ltd
43.	MIDD	The Middleby Corp
44.	MWA	Mueller Water Products Inc
45.	NDSN	Nordson Corp
46.	NNE	NANO Nuclear Energy Inc
47.	NPO	Enpro Inc
48.	OFLX	Omega Flex Inc
49.	OTIS	Otis Worldwide Corp
50.	PH	Parker-Hannifin Corp
51.	PNR	Pentair PLC
52.	PSIX	Power Solutions International Inc
53.	ROK	Rockwell Automation Inc
54.	RRX	Regal Rexnord Corp
55.	SXI	Standex International Corp
56.	SYM	Symbotic Inc
57.	TNC	Tennant Co
58.	WTS	Watts Water Technologies Inc
59.	XMTR	Xometry Inc
60.	XYL	Xylem Inc

20170 Industrial Distribution

20171 Industrial Distribution

1.	AIT	Applied Industrial Technologies Inc
2.	CNM	Core & Main Inc
3.	DNOW	DNOW Inc
4.	DSGR	Distribution Solutions Group Inc
5.	DXPE	DXP Enterprises Inc
6.	FAST	Fastenal Co
7.	FERG	Ferguson Enterprises Inc
8.	GWW	WW Grainger Inc
9.	MSM	MSC Industrial Direct Co Inc
10.	POOL	Pool Corp
11.	QXO	QXO Inc
12.	REZI	Resideo Technologies Inc
13.	SITE	SiteOne Landscape Supply Inc
14.	WCC	WESCO International Inc
15.	WSO	Watsco Inc

20200 Commercial & Professional Services

20210 Commercial Services & Supplies

20211 Waste Management

1.	ALEUP.PA	Europlasma SA
2.	BFSA.DE	Befesa SA
3.	DBG.PA	Derichebourg SA
4.	UMI.BR	Umicore SA
5.	VIE.PA	Veolia Environnement SA
6.	CLH	Clean Harbors Inc
7.	CWST	Casella Waste Systems Inc

- 8. NVRI Enviri Corp
- 9. RSG Republic Services Inc
- 10. WM Waste Management Inc
- 20212 Pollution & Treatment Controls
 - 1. CECO CECO Environmental Corp
 - 2. ERII Energy Recovery Inc
 - 3. FSS Federal Signal Corp
 - 4. FTEK Fuel Tech Inc
 - 5. PCT PureCycle Technologies Inc
 - 6. VLTO Veralto Corp
 - 7. ZWS Zurn Elkay Water Solutions Corp
- 20213 Business Equipment & Supplies
 - 1. EBF Ennis Inc
- 20214 Security & Protection Services
 - 1. ADT ADT Inc
 - 2. ALLE Allegion PLC
 - 3. BCO The Brink's Co
 - 4. BRC Brady Corp
 - 5. CXW CoreCivic Inc
 - 6. GEO The GEO Group Inc
 - 7. MSA MSA Safety Inc
 - 8. NSSC Napco Security Technologies Inc
- 20215 Rental & Leasing Services
 - 1. AL Air Lease Corp
 - 2. CAR Avis Budget Group Inc
 - 3. FTAI FTAI Aviation Ltd
 - 4. GATX GATX Corp
 - 5. HTZ Hertz Global Holdings Inc
 - 6. MGRC McGrath RentCorp
 - 7. PRG PROG Holdings Inc
 - 8. R Ryder System Inc
 - 9. UHAL U-Haul Holding Co
 - 10. URI United Rentals Inc
 - 11. VSTS Vestis Corp
 - 12. WLFC Willis Lease Finance Corp
 - 13. WSC WillScot Holdings Corp

20220 Professional Services

- 20221 Staffing & Employment Services
 - 1. ALFRE.PA Freelance.com SA
 - 2. BRNL.AS Brunel International NV
 - 3. RAND.AS Randstad NV
 - 4. BBSI Barrett Business Services Inc
 - 5. HSII Heidrick & Struggles International Inc
 - 6. KELYA Kelly Services Inc
 - 7. KFY Korn Ferry
 - 8. MAN ManpowerGroup Inc
 - 9. NSP Insperity Inc
 - 10. RHI Robert Half Inc
- 20222 Consulting Services
 - 1. BVI.PA Bureau Veritas SA
 - 2. BAH Booz Allen Hamilton Holding Corp

3.	CRAI	CRA International Inc
4.	DGNX	Diginex Ltd
5.	EFX	Equifax Inc
6.	FCN	FTI Consulting Inc
7.	FORR	Forrester Research Inc
8.	GRNQ	Greenpro Capital Corp
9.	HURN	Huron Consulting Group Inc
10.	ICFI	ICF International Inc
11.	VRSK	Verisk Analytics Inc

20223 Specialty Business Services

1.	INPST.AS	InPost SA
2.	REN.AS	RELX PLC
3.	SW.PA	Sodexo SA
4.	TEP.PA	Teleperformance SE
5.	WKL.AS	Wolters Kluwer NV
6.	ABM	ABM Industries Inc
7.	AMTM	Amentum Holdings Inc
8.	ARMK	Aramark
9.	AZZ	AZZ Inc
10.	CMPR	Cimpres PLC
11.	CPRT	Copart Inc
12.	CTAS	Cintas Corp
13.	DLB	Dolby Laboratories Inc
14.	FA	First Advantage Corp
15.	GPN	Global Payments Inc
16.	LZ	LegalZoom.com Inc
17.	MMS	Maximus Inc
18.	RBA	RB Global Inc
19.	TH	Target Hospitality Corp
20.	TRI	Thomson Reuters Corp
21.	TRNS	Transcat Inc
22.	UNF	UniFirst Corp

20300 Transportation**20310 Air Freight & Logistics**

20311 Integrated Freight & Logistics

1.	BPOST.BR	bpost SA
2.	CTT.LS	CTT Correios De Portugal SA
3.	DHL.DE	Deutsche Post AG
4.	PNL.AS	PostNL NV
5.	CHRW	CH Robinson Worldwide Inc
6.	CYRX	Cryoport Inc
7.	EXPD	Expeditors International of Washington Inc
8.	FDX	FedEx Corp
9.	FWRD	Forward Air Corp
10.	GXO	GXO Logistics Inc
11.	HUBG	Hub Group Inc
12.	JBHT	JB Hunt Transport Services Inc
13.	LSTR	Landstar System Inc
14.	PBI	Pitney Bowes Inc
15.	RLGT	Radiant Logistics Inc
16.	UPS	United Parcel Service Inc

20320 Passenger Airlines

20321 Airlines

1. AF.PA Air France-KLM SA
2. LHA.DE Deutsche Lufthansa AG
3. AAL American Airlines Group Inc
4. ALGT Allegiant Travel Co
5. ALK Alaska Air Group Inc
6. DAL Delta Air Lines Inc
7. JBLU JetBlue Airways Corp
8. LUV Southwest Airlines Co
9. RYAA Ryanair Holdings PLC
10. SKYW SkyWest Inc
11. SNCY Sun Country Airlines Holdings Inc
12. UAL United Airlines Holdings Inc
13. ULCC Frontier Group Holdings Inc

20330 Marine Transportation

20331 Marine Shipping

1. CCEC Capital Clean Energy Carriers Corp
2. CMRE Costamare Inc
3. DAC Danaos Corp
4. ESEA Euroseas Ltd
5. GNK Genco Shipping & Trading Ltd
6. GOGL Golden Ocean Group Ltd
7. GSL Global Ship Lease Inc
8. KEX Kirby Corp
9. MATX Matson Inc
10. NMM Navios Maritime Partners LP
11. SBLK Star Bulk Carriers Corp
12. SHIP Seenergy Maritime Holdings Corp
13. SMHI SEACOR Marine Holdings Inc
14. ZIM ZIM Integrated Shipping Services Ltd

20340 Ground Transportation

20341 Railroads

1. ALO.PA Alstom SA
2. GET.PA Getlink SE
3. CSX CSX Corp
4. GBX The Greenbrier Companies Inc
5. NSC Norfolk Southern Corp
6. TRN Trinity Industries Inc
7. UNP Union Pacific Corp
8. WAB Westinghouse Air Brake Technologies Corp

20342 Trucking

1. ARCB ArcBest Corp
2. HTLD Heartland Express Inc
3. KNX Knight-Swift Transportation Holdings Inc
4. MRTN Marten Transport Ltd
5. ODFL Old Dominion Freight Line Inc
6. RXO RXO Inc
7. SAIA Saia Inc
8. SNDR Schneider National Inc
9. ULH Universal Logistics Holdings Inc

- 10. WERN Werner Enterprises Inc
- 11. XPO XPO Inc

20350 Transportation Infrastructure

- 20351 Airports & Air Services
 - 1. ADP.PA Aeroports de Paris SA
 - 2. FRA.DE Fraport AG
 - 3. ASLE AerSale Corp
 - 4. CAAP Corporación América Airports SA
 - 5. JOBY Joby Aviation Inc
 - 6. SRTA Strata Critical Medical Inc

25000 Consumer Cyclical

25100 Automobiles & Components

25110 Automobile Components

- 25111 Auto Parts
 - 1. CON.DE Continental AG
 - 2. FR.PA Valeo SE
 - 3. HLE.DE HELLA GmbH & Co KGaA
 - 4. KBX.DE Knorr Bremse AG
 - 5. ML.PA CGE Michelin SCA
 - 6. PVL.PA Plastiques du Val de Loire
 - 7. AAP Advance Auto Parts Inc
 - 8. ADNT Adient PLC
 - 9. ALSN Allison Transmission Holdings Inc
 - 10. ALV Autoliv Inc
 - 11. APTV Aptiv PLC
 - 12. AXL American Axle & Manufacturing Holdings Inc
 - 13. AZO AutoZone Inc
 - 14. BWA BorgWarner Inc
 - 15. DAN Dana Inc
 - 16. DORM Dorman Products Inc
 - 17. FOXF Fox Factory Holding Corp
 - 18. GNTX Gentex Corp
 - 19. GPC Genuine Parts Co
 - 20. GT The Goodyear Tire & Rubber Co
 - 21. GTX Garrett Motion Inc
 - 22. INVZ Innoviz Technologies Ltd
 - 23. LEA Lear Corp
 - 24. LKQ LKQ Corp
 - 25. MBLY Mobileye Global Inc
 - 26. MNRO Monro Inc
 - 27. MVST Microvast Holdings Inc
 - 28. ORLY O'Reilly Automotive Inc
 - 29. PHIN PHINIA Inc
 - 30. QS QuantumScape Corp
 - 31. SMP Standard Motor Products Inc
 - 32. THRM Gentherm Inc
 - 33. VC Visteon Corp
 - 34. XPEL XPEL Inc

25120 Automobiles

25121 Auto Manufacturers

1. BMW.DE Bayerische Motoren Werke AG
2. BMW3.DE Bayerische Motoren Werke AG
3. MBG.DE Mercedes Benz Group AG
4. P911.DE Dr Ing h.c F Porsche AG
5. PAH3.DE Porsche Automobil Holding SE
6. RNO.PA Renault SA
7. SCT.LS Toyota Caetano Portugal SA
8. STLAP.PA Stellantis NV
9. VOW.DE Volkswagen AG
10. VOW3.DE Volkswagen AG
11. AIIO Roboai Inc
12. CENN Cenntro Inc
13. F Ford Motor Co
14. GGR Gogoro Inc
15. GM General Motors Co
16. LCID Lucid Group Inc
17. LI Li Auto Inc
18. NWTN Roboai Inc
19. PSNY Polestar Automotive Holding UK PLC
20. RIVN Rivian Automotive Inc
21. TSLA Tesla Inc
22. VFS VinFast Auto Ltd

25200 Consumer Cyclical & Apparel

25210 Household Durables

25211 Residential Construction

1. KOF.PA Kaufman & Broad SA
2. CVCO Cavco Industries Inc
3. DFH Dream Finders Homes Inc
4. DHI DR Horton Inc
5. GRBK Green Brick Partners Inc
6. IBP Installed Building Products Inc
7. KBH KB Home
8. LEN Lennar Corp
9. LEN-B Lennar Corp
10. LGIH LGI Homes Inc
11. MHO M-I Homes Inc
12. MTH Meritage Homes Corp
13. NVR NVR Inc
14. PHM PulteGroup Inc
15. SKY Champion Homes Inc
16. TMHC Taylor Morrison Home Corp
17. TOL Toll Brothers Inc
18. TPH Tri Pointe Homes Inc

25220 Leisure Products

25221 Leisure

1. BFIT.AS Basic-Fit NV
2. AS Amer Sports Inc
3. FUN Six Flags Entertainment Corp
4. GOLF Acushnet Holdings Corp

- 5. HAS Hasbro Inc
- 6. MAT Mattel Inc
- 7. MODG Topgolf Callaway Brands Corp
- 8. OSW OneSpaWorld Holdings Ltd
- 9. PLNT Planet Fitness Inc
- 10. PTON Peloton Interactive Inc
- 11. YETI YETI Holdings Inc

25222 Recreational Vehicles

- 1. BEN.PA Bénéteau SA
- 2. TRI.PA Trigano SA
- 3. BC Brunswick Corp
- 4. DOOO BRP Inc
- 5. HOG Harley-Davidson Inc
- 6. LCII LCI Industries
- 7. MBUU Malibu Boats Inc
- 8. PII Polaris Inc
- 9. THO THOR Industries Inc
- 10. WGO Winnebago Industries Inc

25230 Textiles Apparel & Luxury Goods

25231 Luxury Goods

- 1. BIJ.DE Bijou Brigitte modische Accessoires AG
- 2. DPT.PA ST Dupont SA
- 3. KER.PA Kering SA
- 4. MC.PA LVMH Moët Hennessy-Louis Vuitton SE
- 5. RMS.PA Hermès International SCA
- 6. CPRI Capri Holdings Ltd
- 7. REAL The RealReal Inc
- 8. SIG Signet Jewelers Ltd
- 9. TPR Tapestry Inc

25232 Apparel Manufacturing

- 1. BOSS.DE Hugo Boss AG
- 2. VAN.BR Van de Velde NV
- 3. COLM Columbia Sportswear Co
- 4. GIII G-III Apparel Group Ltd
- 5. HBI Hanesbrands Inc
- 6. KTB Kontoor Brands Inc
- 7. OXM Oxford Industries Inc
- 8. PVH PVH Corp
- 9. RL Ralph Lauren Corp
- 10. UA Under Armour Inc
- 11. UAA Under Armour Inc
- 12. VFC VF Corp

25233 Footwear & Accessories

- 1. ADS.DE adidas AG
- 2. PUM.DE PUMA SE
- 3. BIRK Birkenstock Holding PLC
- 4. CROX Crocs Inc
- 5. DECK Deckers Outdoor Corp
- 6. NKE NIKE Inc
- 7. ONON On Holding AG
- 8. SHOO Steven Madden Ltd
- 9. SKX Skechers USA Inc

10. WWW Wolverine World Wide Inc

25234 Textile Manufacturing

1. AIN Albany International Corp

25300 Consumer Cyclical Services

25310 Hotels Restaurants & Leisure

25311 Gambling

1. ACEL Accel Entertainment Inc

2. BRSL Brightstar Lottery

3. CDRO Codere Online Luxembourg SA

4. CHDN Churchill Downs Inc

5. DKNG DraftKings Inc

6. FLUT Flutter Entertainment PLC

7. GAMB Gambling.com Group Ltd

8. INSE Inspired Entertainment Inc

9. LNW Light & Wonder Inc

10. RSI Rush Street Interactive Inc

11. SBET SharpLink Gaming Inc

12. SGHC Super Group (SGHC) Ltd

25312 Resorts & Casinos

1. BYD Boyd Gaming Corp

2. CZR Caesars Entertainment Inc

3. GDEN Golden Entertainment Inc

4. HGV Hilton Grand Vacations Inc

5. LVS Las Vegas Sands Corp

6. MCRI Monarch Casino & Resort Inc

7. MGM MGM Resorts International

8. MLCO Melco Resorts & Entertainment Ltd

9. MTN Vail Resorts Inc

10. PENN PENN Entertainment Inc

11. RRR Red Rock Resorts Inc

12. VAC Marriott Vacations Worldwide Corp

13. WYNN Wynn Resorts Ltd

25313 Travel Services

1. TUI1.DE TUI AG

2. ABNB Airbnb Inc

3. BKNG Booking Holdings Inc

4. CCL Carnival Corp & PLC

5. EXPE Expedia Group Inc

6. MMYT MakeMyTrip Ltd

7. NCLH Norwegian Cruise Line Holdings Ltd

8. PRSU Pursuit Attractions and Hospitality Inc

9. RCL Royal Caribbean Cruises Ltd

10. TCOM Trip.com Group Ltd

11. TNL Travel + Leisure Co

12. TRIP Tripadvisor Inc

13. VIK Viking Holdings Ltd

25314 Lodging

1. AC.PA Accor SA

2. ATAT Atour Lifestyle Holdings Ltd

3. CHH Choice Hotels International Inc

4. H Hyatt Hotels Corp

- 5. HLT Hilton Worldwide Holdings Inc
- 6. HTHH H World Group Ltd
- 7. MAR Marriott International Inc
- 8. WH Wyndham Hotels & Resorts Inc

25315 Restaurants

- 1. ELIOR.PA Elixir Group SA
- 2. HFG.DE HelloFresh SE
- 3. IBS.LS Ibersol SGPS
- 4. BJRI BJ's Restaurants Inc
- 5. BLMN Bloomin' Brands Inc
- 6. BROS Dutch Bros Inc
- 7. CAKE The Cheesecake Factory Inc
- 8. CAVA CAVA Group Inc
- 9. CBRL Cracker Barrel Old Country Store Inc
- 10. CMG Chipotle Mexican Grill Inc
- 11. DPZ Domino's Pizza Inc
- 12. DRI Darden Restaurants Inc
- 13. EAT Brinker International Inc
- 14. FWRG First Watch Restaurant Group Inc
- 15. JACK Jack in the Box Inc
- 16. KRUS Kura Sushi USA Inc
- 17. MCD McDonald's Corp
- 18. PZZA Papa John's International Inc
- 19. QSR Restaurant Brands International Inc
- 20. SBUX Starbucks Corp
- 21. SHAK Shake Shack Inc
- 22. TXRH Texas Roadhouse Inc
- 23. WEN The Wendy's Co
- 24. WING Wingstop Inc
- 25. YUM Yum! Brands Inc

25320 Diversified Consumer Services

25321 Education & Training Services

- 1. AFYA Afya Ltd
- 2. APEI American Public Education Inc
- 3. ATGE Adtalem Global Education Inc
- 4. GHC Graham Holdings Co
- 5. LAUR Laureate Education Inc
- 6. LINC Lincoln Educational Services Corp
- 7. LOPE Grand Canyon Education Inc
- 8. LRN Stride Inc
- 9. PRDO Perdoceo Education Corp
- 10. STRA Strategic Education Inc
- 11. UDMY Udemy Inc

25322 Personal Services

- 1. BFAM Bright Horizons Family Solutions Inc
- 2. CSV Carriage Services Inc
- 3. FTDR Frontdoor Inc
- 4. HRB H&R Block Inc
- 5. MED Medifast Inc
- 6. RGS Regis Corp
- 7. ROL Rollins Inc
- 8. SCI Service Corp International

25400 Consumer Cyclical Distribution & Retail

25410 Internet Retail

- 25411 Internet Retail
 - 1. DHER.DE Delivery Hero SE
 - 2. SRP.PA SRP Groupe SA
 - 3. TKWY.AS Just Eat Takeawaycom NV
 - 4. ZAL.DE Zalando SE
 - 5. AMZN Amazon.com Inc
 - 6. CART Maplebear Inc
 - 7. CHWY Chewy Inc
 - 8. CPNG Coupang Inc
 - 9. DASH DoorDash Inc
 - 10. EBAY eBay Inc
 - 11. ETSY Etsy Inc
 - 12. GLBE Global-E Online Ltd
 - 13. JD JD.com Inc
 - 14. LQDT Liquidity Services Inc
 - 15. MELI MercadoLibre Inc
 - 16. NEGG Newegg Commerce Inc
 - 17. PDD PDD Holdings Inc
 - 18. W Wayfair Inc

25420 Broadline Retail

- 25421 Department Stores
 - 1. DDS Dillard's Inc
 - 2. KSS Kohl's Corp
 - 3. M Macy's Inc
 - 4. PLBL Polibeli Group Ltd

25430 Specialty Retail

- 25431 Apparel Retail
 - 1. ALFBA.PA Fashion Bel Air SA
 - 2. AEO American Eagle Outfitters Inc
 - 3. ANF Abercrombie & Fitch Co
 - 4. BKE The Buckle Inc
 - 5. BOOT Boot Barn Holdings Inc
 - 6. BURL Burlington Stores Inc
 - 7. CAL Caleres Inc
 - 8. CRI Carter's Inc
 - 9. FL Foot Locker Inc
 - 10. GAP The Gap Inc
 - 11. GES Guess? Inc
 - 12. LULU lululemon athletica Inc
 - 13. ROST Ross Stores Inc
 - 14. SCVL Shoe Carnival Inc
 - 15. SFIX Stitch Fix Inc
 - 16. TJX The TJX Companies Inc
 - 17. URBN Urban Outfitters Inc
 - 18. VSCO Victoria's Secret & Co
- 25432 Home Improvement Retail
 - 1. FND Floor & Decor Holdings Inc
 - 2. HD The Home Depot Inc
 - 3. HVT Haverty Furniture Companies Inc

4.	LIVE	Live Ventures Inc
5.	LOW	Lowe's Companies Inc
6.	TTSH	Tile Shop Holdings Inc
25433	Specialty Retail	
1.	ALHRS.PA	Hydrogen-Refueling-Solutions SA
2.	CEC.DE	Ceconomy AG
3.	FNAC.PA	Fnac Darty SA
4.	MMB.PA	Lagardere SA
5.	ASO	Academy Sports and Outdoors Inc
6.	BBWI	Bath & Body Works Inc
7.	BBY	Best Buy Co Inc
8.	CASY	Casey's General Stores Inc
9.	DKS	DICK'S Sporting Goods Inc
10.	EYE	National Vision Holdings Inc
11.	FIVE	Five Below Inc
12.	GME	GameStop Corp
13.	HZO	MarineMax Inc
14.	MUSA	Murphy USA Inc
15.	ODP	The ODP Corp
16.	OLPX	Olaplex Holdings Inc
17.	RH	RH
18.	SBH	Sally Beauty Holdings Inc
19.	TSCO	Tractor Supply Co
20.	ULTA	Ulta Beauty Inc
21.	WINA	Winmark Corp
22.	WOOF	Petco Health and Wellness Co Inc
23.	WSM	Williams-Sonoma Inc
25434	Auto & Truck Dealerships	
1.	DIE.BR	D'Ieteren Group SA
2.	ABG	Asbury Automotive Group Inc
3.	ACVA	ACV Auctions Inc
4.	AN	AutoNation Inc
5.	CARG	CarGurus Inc
6.	CVNA	Carvana Co
7.	DRVN	Driven Brands Holdings Inc
8.	GPI	Group 1 Automotive Inc
9.	KAR	OPENLANE Inc
10.	KMX	CarMax Inc
11.	LAD	Lithia Motors Inc
12.	MCW	Mister Car Wash Inc
13.	PAG	Penske Automotive Group Inc
14.	RUSHA	Rush Enterprises Inc
15.	SAH	Sonic Automotive Inc
16.	VVV	Valvoline Inc
25435	Furnishings Fixtures & Appliances	
1.	SK.PA	SEB SA
2.	VAF.LS	Vista Alegre Atlantis SGPS
3.	AMWD	American Woodmark Corp
4.	ETD	Ethan Allen Interiors Inc
5.	HNI	HNI Corp
6.	LEG	Leggett & Platt Inc
7.	LZB	La-Z-Boy Inc

8.	MBC	MasterBrand Inc
9.	MHK	Mohawk Industries Inc
10.	MLKN	MillerKnoll Inc
11.	PATK	Patrick Industries Inc
12.	SGI	Somnigroup International Inc
13.	SN	SharkNinja Inc
14.	TILE	Interface Inc
15.	WHR	Whirlpool Corp

30000 Consumer Defensive

30100 Consumer Defensive Distribution & Retail

30110 Consumer Defensive Distribution & Retail

30111 Food Distribution

1.	ACOMO.AS	Acomo NV
2.	JMT.LS	Jerónimo Martins SGPS
3.	ANDE	The Andersons Inc
4.	AVO	Mission Produce Inc
5.	CHEF	The Chefs' Warehouse Inc
6.	PFGC	Performance Food Group Co
7.	SPTN	SpartanNash Co
8.	SYU	Sysco Corp
9.	UNFI	United Natural Foods Inc
10.	USFD	US Foods Holding Corp

30112 Grocery Stores

1.	AD.AS	Koninklijke Ahold Delhaize NV
2.	CA.PA	Carrefour SA
3.	CO.PA	Casino Guichard-Perrachon SA
4.	SON.LS	Sonae SGPS
5.	ACI	Albertsons Companies Inc
6.	DNUT	Krispy Kreme Inc
7.	GO	Grocery Outlet Holding Corp
8.	IMKTA	Ingles Markets Inc
9.	KR	The Kroger Co
10.	SFM	Sprouts Farmers Market Inc

30113 Discount Stores

1.	BJ	BJ's Wholesale Club Holdings Inc
2.	COST	Costco Wholesale Corp
3.	DG	Dollar General Corp
4.	DLTR	Dollar Tree Inc
5.	OLLI	Ollie's Bargain Outlet Holdings Inc
6.	PSMT	PriceSmart Inc
7.	TGT	Target Corp
8.	WMT	Walmart Inc

30200 Food Beverage & Tobacco

30210 Beverages

30211 Beverages-Brewers

1.	ABI.BR	Anheuser-Busch InBev SA
2.	HEIA.AS	Heineken NV
3.	SAM	The Boston Beer Co Inc

- 4. STZ Constellation Brands Inc
- 5. TAP Molson Coors Beverage Co
- 30212 Beverages-Wineries & Distilleries
 - 1. RCO.PA Rémy Cointreau SA
 - 2. RI.PA Pernod Ricard SA
 - 3. SBT.PA Oeneo SA
 - 4. BF-A Brown-Forman Corp
 - 5. BF-B Brown-Forman Corp
 - 6. CWGL Crimson Wine Group Ltd
 - 7. EPSM Epsium Enterprise Ltd
 - 8. MGPI MGP Ingredients Inc
- 30213 Beverages-Non-Alcoholic
 - 1. CCEP Coca-Cola Europacific Partners PLC
 - 2. CELH Celsius Holdings Inc
 - 3. COCO The Vita Coco Co Inc
 - 4. COKE Coca-Cola Consolidated Inc
 - 5. FIZZ National Beverage Corp
 - 6. KDP Keurig Dr Pepper Inc
 - 7. KO The Coca-Cola Co
 - 8. MNST Monster Beverage Corp
 - 9. PEP PepsiCo Inc
 - 10. PRMB Primo Brands Corp

30220 Food Products

- 30221 Farm Products
 - 1. ALAGR.PA AgroGeneration SA
 - 2. ADM Archer-Daniels-Midland Co
 - 3. BG Bunge Global SA
 - 4. CALM Cal-Maine Foods Inc
 - 5. FDP Fresh Del Monte Produce Inc
 - 6. TSN Tyson Foods Inc
 - 7. VITL Vital Farms Inc
- 30222 Packaged Foods
 - 1. BN.PA Danone SA
 - 2. BON.PA Bonduelle SCA
 - 3. FFARM.AS ForFarmers NV
 - 4. JDEP.AS JDE Peet's NV
 - 5. LOTB.BR Lotus Bakeries NV
 - 6. BGS B&G Foods Inc
 - 7. BRBR BellRing Brands Inc
 - 8. BRID Bridgford Foods Corp
 - 9. CAG Conagra Brands Inc
 - 10. CENT Central Garden & Pet Co
 - 11. CENTA Central Garden & Pet Co
 - 12. CPB The Campbell's Co
 - 13. DAR Darling Ingredients Inc
 - 14. FLO Flowers Foods Inc
 - 15. FRPT Freshpet Inc
 - 16. GIS General Mills Inc
 - 17. HAIN The Hain Celestial Group Inc
 - 18. HRL Hormel Foods Corp
 - 19. INGR Ingredion Inc
 - 20. JBSS John B Sanfilippo & Son Inc

21. JJSF J&J Snack Foods Corp
22. K Kellanova
23. KHC The Kraft Heinz Co
24. KLG WK Kellogg Co
25. LW Lamb Weston Holdings Inc
26. MKC McCormick & Co Inc
27. MZTI The Marzetti Co
28. POST Post Holdings Inc
29. PPC Pilgrim's Pride Corp
30. SENE Seneca Foods Corp
31. SFD Smithfield Foods Inc
32. SJM The J M Smucker Co
33. SMPL The Simply Good Foods Co
34. THS TreeHouse Foods Inc
35. USNA USANA Health Sciences Inc

30223 Confectioners

1. HSY The Hershey Co
2. MDLZ Mondelez International Inc
3. TR Tootsie Roll Industries Inc

30230 Tobacco

30231 Tobacco

1. MO Altria Group Inc
2. PM Philip Morris International Inc
3. TPB Turning Point Brands Inc
4. UVV Universal Corp

30300 Household & Personal Products

30310 Household & Personal Products

30311 Household & Personal Products

1. ALMAS.PA Mastrad SA
2. BB.PA Société BIC SA
3. BEI.DE Beiersdorf AG
4. HEN3.DE Henkel AG & Co KGaA
5. ONTEX.BR Ontex Group NV
6. OR.PA L'Oréal SA
7. UNA.AS Unilever PLC
8. CHD Church & Dwight Co Inc
9. CL Colgate-Palmolive Co
10. CLX The Clorox Co
11. COTY Coty Inc
12. EL The Estée Lauder Companies Inc
13. ELF elf Beauty Inc
14. EPC Edgewell Personal Care Co
15. HELE Helen of Troy Ltd
16. IPAR Interparfums Inc
17. KMB Kimberly-Clark Corp
18. KVUE Kenvue Inc
19. NWL Newell Brands Inc
20. PG The Procter & Gamble Co

35000 Healthcare**35100 Healthcare Equipment & Services****35110 Healthcare Equipment & Supplies**

35111 Medical Devices

1. ALCAR.PA Carmat SA
2. ALIMP.PA Implanet SA
3. EUZ.DE Eckert & Ziegler SE
4. PHIA.AS Koninklijke Philips NV
5. SHL.DE Siemens Healthineers AG
6. ABT Abbott Laboratories
7. AHCO AdaptHealth Corp
8. AORT Artivion Inc
9. ATEC Alphatec Holdings Inc
10. AVNS Avanos Medical Inc
11. BIO Bio-Rad Laboratories Inc
12. BRKR Bruker Corp
13. BSX Boston Scientific Corp
14. BVS Bioventus Inc
15. CERS Cerus Corp
16. CNMD CONMED Corp
17. CTKB Cytek Biosciences Inc
18. DXCM DexCom Inc
19. ENOV Enovis Corp
20. ESTA Establishment Labs Holdings Inc
21. EW Edwards Lifesciences Corp
22. GKOS Glaukos Corp
23. GMED Globus Medical Inc
24. HAE Haemonetics Corp
25. IART Integra LifeSciences Holdings Corp
26. INMD InMode Ltd
27. INSP Inspire Medical Systems Inc
28. IRMD IRADIMED CORPORATION
29. IRTC iRhythm Technologies Inc
30. ITGR Integer Holdings Corp
31. LIVN LivaNova PLC
32. MASI Masimo Corp
33. MDT Medtronic PLC
34. NVCR NovoCure Ltd
35. PEN Penumbra Inc
36. PODD Insulet Corp
37. PRCT PROCEPT BioRobotics Corp
38. QDEL QuidelOrtho Corp
39. RXST RxSight Inc
40. STE STERIS PLC
41. SYK Stryker Corp
42. TMDX TransMedics Group Inc
43. TNDM Tandem Diabetes Care Inc
44. UFPT UFP Technologies Inc
45. ZBH Zimmer Biomet Holdings Inc

35112 Medical Instruments & Supplies

1. AFX.DE Carl Zeiss Meditec AG
2. ALSAF.PA Safe Orthopaedics SA

3. AMPLI.PA Amplitude Surgical SA
4. DIM.PA Sartorius Stedim Biotech SA
5. EL.PA EssilorLuxottica SA
6. GXI.DE Gerresheimer AG
7. SRT.DE Sartorius AG
8. SRT3.DE Sartorius AG
9. ALGN Align Technology Inc
10. ATR AptarGroup Inc
11. ATRC AtriCure Inc
12. AVTR Avantor Inc
13. AZTA Azenta Inc
14. BAX Baxter International Inc
15. BDJ Becton Dickinson and Co
16. BLFS BioLife Solutions Inc
17. COO The Cooper Companies Inc
18. EMBC Embecta Corp
19. HOLX Hologic Inc
20. ICUI ICU Medical Inc
21. ISRG Intuitive Surgical Inc
22. KMTS Kestra Medical Technologies Ltd
23. LMAT LeMaitre Vascular Inc
24. MMSI Merit Medical Systems Inc
25. NVST Envista Holdings Corp
26. PLSE Pulse Biosciences Inc
27. RGEN Repligen Corp
28. RMD ResMed Inc
29. SOLV Solventum Corp
30. STAA STAAR Surgical Co
31. TFX Teleflex Inc
32. WST West Pharmaceutical Services Inc
33. XRAY DENTSPLY SIRONA Inc

35120 Healthcare Providers & Services

35121 Medical Distribution

1. CAH Cardinal Health Inc
2. COR Cencora Inc
3. EMPG Empro Group Inc
4. HSIC Henry Schein Inc
5. MCK McKesson Corp
6. OMI Owens & Minor Inc

35122 Pharmaceutical Retailers

1. RDC.DE Redcare Pharmacy NV
2. WBA Walgreens Boots Alliance Inc

35123 Diagnostics & Research

1. BIM.PA bioMérieux SA
2. ERF.PA Eurofins Scientific SE
3. LBIRD.PA Lumibird SA
4. QIA.DE Qiagen NV
5. A Agilent Technologies Inc
6. CDNA CareDx Inc
7. CRL Charles River Laboratories International
8. DGX Quest Diagnostics Inc
9. DHR Danaher Corp

10.	EXAS	Exact Sciences Corp
11.	FLGT	Fulgent Genetics Inc
12.	GH	Guardant Health Inc
13.	GRAL	GRAIL Inc
14.	ICLR	ICON Public Ltd Co
15.	IDXX	IDEXX Laboratories Inc
16.	ILMN	Illumina Inc
17.	IQV	IQVIA Holdings Inc
18.	LH	Labcorp Holdings Inc
19.	MEDP	Medpace Holdings Inc
20.	MTD	Mettler-Toledo International Inc
21.	MYGN	Myriad Genetics Inc
22.	NEO	NeoGenomics Inc
23.	NEOG	Neogen Corp
24.	NTRA	Natera Inc
25.	OPK	OPKO Health Inc
26.	QGEN	Qiagen NV
27.	RDNT	RadNet Inc
28.	RVTY	Revvity Inc
29.	SHC	Sotera Health Co
30.	TMO	Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc
31.	TWST	Twist Bioscience Corp
32.	VCYT	Veracyte Inc
33.	WAT	Waters Corp
34.	WGS	GeneDx Holdings Corp
35124	Medical Care Facilities	
1.	FME.DE	Fresenius Medical Care AG
2.	FRE.DE	Fresenius SE & Co KGaA
3.	RHK.DE	RHÖN KLINIKUM AG
4.	ACHC	Acadia Healthcare Co Inc
5.	ADUS	Addus HomeCare Corp
6.	AIRS	AirSculpt Technologies Inc
7.	AMED	Amedisys Inc
8.	AMN	AMN Healthcare Services Inc
9.	ASTH	Astrana Health Inc
10.	AVAH	Aveanna Healthcare Holdings Inc
11.	CHE	Chemed Corp
12.	CON	Concentra Group Holdings Parent Inc
13.	DVA	DaVita Inc
14.	EHC	Encompass Health Corp
15.	ENSG	The Ensign Group Inc
16.	HCA	HCA Healthcare Inc
17.	HCSG	Healthcare Services Group Inc
18.	LFST	LifeStance Health Group Inc
19.	MD	Pediatrics Medical Group Inc
20.	NHC	National HealthCare Corp
21.	OPCH	Option Care Health Inc
22.	PIII	P3 Health Partners Inc
23.	PNTG	The Pennant Group Inc
24.	SEM	Select Medical Holdings Corp
25.	SGRY	Surgery Partners Inc
26.	THC	Tenet Healthcare Corp
27.	UHS	Universal Health Services Inc

28. USPH US Physical Therapy Inc

35125 Healthcare Plans

1. ALHC Alignment Healthcare Inc
2. CI The Cigna Group
3. CLOV Clover Health Investments Corp
4. CNC Centene Corp
5. CVS CVS Health Corp
6. ELV Elevance Health Inc
7. HUM Humana Inc
8. MOH Molina Healthcare Inc
9. PGNY Progyny Inc
10. UNH UnitedHealth Group Inc

35130 Healthcare Technology

35131 Health Information Services

1. ALINS.PA Intrasense SA
2. BTSG BrightSpring Health Services Inc
3. CERT Certara Inc
4. DOCS Doximity Inc
5. GEHC GE HealthCare Technologies Inc
6. HQY HealthEquity Inc
7. HSTM HealthStream Inc
8. NRC National Research Corp
9. OMCL Omnicell Inc
10. PINC Premier Inc
11. PRVA Privia Health Group Inc
12. SDGR Schrödinger Inc
13. SLP Simulations Plus Inc
14. SOPH SOPHiA GENETICS SA
15. TEM Tempus AI Inc
16. TXG 10x Genomics Inc
17. VEEV Veeva Systems Inc
18. WAY Waystar Holding Corp

35200 Pharmaceuticals & Biotechnology

35210 Biotechnology

35211 Biotechnology

1. ADOC.PA Adocia SA
2. ALBPS.PA Biophytis SA
3. ALCLS.PA Collectis SA
4. ALGEN.PA genOway SA
5. ALINT.PA IntegraGen SA
6. ALNEV.PA Neovacs SA
7. ALQGC.PA Quantum Genomics SA
8. ALSEN.PA Sensorion SA
9. ARGX.BR argenx SE
10. GLPG.AS Galapagos NV
11. GNFT.PA Genfit SA
12. IPH.PA Innate Pharma SA
13. NANO.PA Nanobiotix SA
14. OSE.PA OSE Immunotherapeutics SA
15. PHARM.AS Pharming Group NV
16. POXEL.PA Poxel SA

17.	SIGHT.PA	GenSight Biologics SA
18.	TNG.PA	Transgene SA
19.	UCB.BR	UCB SA
20.	VLA.PA	Valneva SE
21.	ABCL	AbCellera Biologics Inc
22.	ACAD	ACADIA Pharmaceuticals Inc
23.	ACLX	Arcellx Inc
24.	ACRS	Aclaris Therapeutics Inc
25.	ADMA	ADMA Biologics Inc
26.	ADPT	Adaptive Biotechnologies Corp
27.	AGIO	Agios Pharmaceuticals Inc
28.	AKRO	Akero Therapeutics Inc
29.	ALNY	Alnylam Pharmaceuticals Inc
30.	ANAB	AnaptysBio Inc
31.	APGE	Apogee Therapeutics Inc
32.	APLS	Apellis Pharmaceuticals Inc
33.	APLT	Applied Therapeutics Inc
34.	APM	Aptorum Group Ltd
35.	ARDX	Ardelyx Inc
36.	ARQT	Arcutis Biotherapeutics Inc
37.	ARVN	Arvinas Inc
38.	ARWR	Arrowhead Pharmaceuticals Inc
39.	ASND	Ascendis Pharma A-S
40.	AUPH	Aurinia Pharmaceuticals Inc
41.	AVBP	ArriVent BioPharma Inc
42.	AVIR	Atea Pharmaceuticals Inc
43.	AXSM	Axsome Therapeutics Inc
44.	BBIO	BridgeBio Pharma Inc
45.	BCAX	Bicara Therapeutics Inc
46.	BCYC	Bicycle Therapeutics PLC
47.	BEAM	Beam Therapeutics Inc
48.	BLTE	Belite Bio Inc
49.	BMRN	BioMarin Pharmaceutical Inc
50.	BNTX	BioNTech SE
51.	CAI	Caris Life Sciences Inc
52.	CGEM	Cullinan Therapeutics Inc
53.	CGON	CG Oncology Inc
54.	CLDX	Celldex Therapeutics Inc
55.	CNTA	Centessa Pharmaceuticals PLC
56.	COGT	Cogent Biosciences Inc
57.	CORT	Corcept Therapeutics Inc
58.	CPRX	Catalyst Pharmaceuticals Inc
59.	CRGX	CARGO Therapeutics Inc
60.	CRMD	CorMedix Inc
61.	CRNX	Crinetics Pharmaceuticals Inc
62.	CRSP	CRISPR Therapeutics AG
63.	CVAC	CureVac NV
64.	CYCN	Cyclerion Therapeutics Inc
65.	CYTK	Cytokinetics Inc
66.	DAWN	Day One Biopharmaceuticals Inc
67.	DNLI	Denali Therapeutics Inc
68.	DSGN	Design Therapeutics Inc
69.	DYN	Dyne Therapeutics Inc
70.	ELVN	Enliven Therapeutics Inc

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

71. ETNB	89bio Inc
72. EWTX	Edgewise Therapeutics Inc
73. EXEL	Exelixis Inc
74. FBRX	Forte Biosciences Inc
75. FOLD	Amicus Therapeutics Inc
76. FTRE	Fortrea Holdings Inc
77. GALT	Galectin Therapeutics Inc
78. GERN	Geron Corp
79. GHRS	GH Research PLC
80. GLUE	Monte Rosa Therapeutics Inc
81. GMAB	Genmab A-S
82. GPCR	Structure Therapeutics Inc
83. HALO	Halozyne Therapeutics Inc
84. HRMY	Harmony Biosciences Holdings Inc
85. IBRX	ImmunityBio Inc
86. IDYA	IDEAYA Biosciences Inc
87. IMCR	Immunocore Holdings PLC
88. IMNM	Immunome Inc
89. IMTX	Immatics NV
90. IMVT	Immunovant Inc
91. INBX	Inhibrx Biosciences Inc
92. INCY	Incyte Corp
93. INMB	INmune Bio Inc
94. INSM	Insmed Inc
95. INVA	Innoviva Inc
96. IONS	Ionis Pharmaceuticals Inc
97. IOVA	Iovance Biotherapeutics Inc
98. IRON	Disc Medicine Inc
99. JANX	Janux Therapeutics Inc
100. JAZZ	Jazz Pharmaceuticals PLC
101. KROS	Keros Therapeutics Inc
102. KRYS	Krystal Biotech Inc
103. KURA	Kura Oncology Inc
104. KYMR	Kymera Therapeutics Inc
105. LEGN	Legend Biotech Corp
106. LGND	Ligand Pharmaceuticals Inc
107. LQDA	Liquidia Corp
108. LYEL	Lyell Immunopharma Inc
109. MDGL	Madrigal Pharmaceuticals Inc
110. MIRM	Mirum Pharmaceuticals Inc
111. MLTX	MoonLake Immunotherapeutics
112. MLYS	Mineralys Therapeutics Inc
113. MNKD	MannKind Corp
114. MRNA	Moderna Inc
115. MRUS	Merus NV
116. MRVI	Maravai LifeSciences Holdings Inc
117. MTSR	Metsera Inc
118. NAGE	Niagen Bioscience Inc
119. NAMS	NewAmsterdam Pharma Co NV
120. NMRA	Neumora Therapeutics Inc
121. NRIX	Nurix Therapeutics Inc
122. NTLA	Intellia Therapeutics Inc
123. NUVL	Nuvalent Inc
124. NVAX	Novavax Inc

125.	OABI	OmniAb Inc
126.	OCUL	Ocular Therapeutix Inc
127.	ONC	BeOne Medicines AG
128.	PCVX	Vaxcyte Inc
129.	PHAT	Phathom Pharmaceuticals Inc
130.	PHVS	Pharvaris NV
131.	PRAX	Praxis Precision Medicines Inc
132.	PRTA	Prothena Corp PLC
133.	PTCT	PTC Therapeutics Inc
134.	PTGX	Protagonist Therapeutics Inc
135.	RARE	Ultragenyx Pharmaceutical Inc
136.	RCKT	Rocket Pharmaceuticals Inc
137.	RCUS	Arcus Biosciences Inc
138.	REGN	Regeneron Pharmaceuticals Inc
139.	RLAY	Relay Therapeutics Inc
140.	RNA	Avidity Biosciences Inc
141.	RNTX	Rein Therapeutics Inc
142.	ROIV	Roivant Sciences Ltd
143.	RPRX	Royalty Pharma PLC
144.	RVMD	Revolution Medicines Inc
145.	RXXR	Recursion Pharmaceuticals Inc
146.	RYTM	Rhythm Pharmaceuticals Inc
147.	SANA	Sana Biotechnology Inc
148.	SAVA	Cassava Sciences Inc
149.	SLNO	Soleno Therapeutics Inc
150.	SMMT	Summit Therapeutics Inc
151.	SNDX	Syndax Pharmaceuticals Inc
152.	SPRY	ARS Pharmaceuticals Inc
153.	SRPT	Sarepta Therapeutics Inc
154.	SRRK	Scholar Rock Holding Corp
155.	SVRA	Savara Inc
156.	SYRE	Spyre Therapeutics Inc
157.	TARS	Tarsus Pharmaceuticals Inc
158.	TECH	Bio-Techne Corp
159.	TGTX	TG Therapeutics Inc
160.	TLSA	Tiziana Life Sciences Ltd
161.	TNGX	Tango Therapeutics Inc
162.	TRDA	Entrada Therapeutics Inc
163.	TVTX	Traverse Therapeutics Inc
164.	TYRA	Tyra Biosciences Inc
165.	VCEL	Vericel Corp
166.	VERA	Vera Therapeutics Inc
167.	VIR	Vir Biotechnology Inc
168.	VKTX	Viking Therapeutics Inc
169.	VRDN	Viridian Therapeutics Inc
170.	VRNA	Verona Pharma PLC
171.	VRTX	Vertex Pharmaceuticals Inc
172.	VXRT	Vaxart Inc
173.	WVE	Wave Life Sciences Ltd
174.	XENE	Xenon Pharmaceuticals Inc
175.	XNCR	Xencor Inc
176.	ZLAB	Zai Lab Ltd
177.	ZYME	Zymeworks Inc

35220 Pharmaceuticals

35221 Drug Manufacturers-General

1. BAYN.DE Bayer AG
2. SAN.PA Sanofi
3. VIRP.PA Virbac SA
4. ABBV AbbVie Inc
5. AMGN Amgen Inc
6. AZN AstraZeneca PLC
7. BIIB Biogen Inc
8. BMY Bristol-Myers Squibb Co
9. GILD Gilead Sciences Inc
10. GRFS Grifols SA
11. JNJ Johnson & Johnson
12. LLY Eli Lilly and Co
13. MRK Merck & Co Inc
14. OGN Organon & Co
15. PFE Pfizer Inc
16. SCLX Scilex Holding Co
17. SNY Sanofi

35222 Drug Manufacturers-Specialty & Generic

1. AB.PA AB Science SA
2. EVT.DE Evotec SE
3. FAGR.BR Fagron NV
4. IPN.PA Ipsen SA
5. MRK.DE Merck KGaA
6. AKBA Akebia Therapeutics Inc
7. ALKS Alkermes PLC
8. ALVO Alvotech
9. AMPH Amphastar Pharmaceuticals Inc
10. AMRX Amneal Pharmaceuticals Inc
11. ANIP ANI Pharmaceuticals Inc
12. AVDL Avadel Pharmaceuticals PLC
13. BCRX BioCryst Pharmaceuticals Inc
14. BGM BGM Group Ltd
15. COLL Collegium Pharmaceutical Inc
16. CRON Cronos Group Inc
17. DVAX Dynavax Technologies Corp
18. ELAN Elanco Animal Health Inc
19. HIMS Hims & Hers Health Inc
20. HROW Harrow Inc
21. INDV Indivior PLC
22. KNSA Kiniksa Pharmaceuticals International PLC
23. LNTH Lantheus Holdings Inc
24. NBIX Neurocrine Biosciences Inc
25. PAHC Phibro Animal Health Corp
26. PBH Prestige Consumer Healthcare Inc
27. PCRX Pacira BioSciences Inc
28. PRGO Perrigo Co PLC
29. RGC Regencell Bioscience Holdings Ltd
30. SIGA SIGA Technologies Inc
31. SUPN Supernus Pharmaceuticals Inc
32. TLRY Tilray Brands Inc
33. UTHR United Therapeutics Corp

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|----------|-------------|
| 34. VTRS | Viatrix Inc |
| 35. ZTS | Zoetis Inc |

40000 Financial Services

40100 Banks

40110 Banks

- | | |
|-------|--|
| 40111 | Banks-Diversified |
| 1. | ABN.AS ABN AMRO Bank NV |
| 2. | INGA.AS ING Groep NV |
| 3. | BAC Bank of America Corp |
| 4. | BK The Bank of New York Mellon Corp |
| 5. | C Citigroup Inc |
| 6. | JPM JPMorgan Chase & Co |
| 7. | WFC Wells Fargo & Co |
| 40112 | Banks-Regional |
| 1. | ACA.PA Crédit Agricole SA |
| 2. | BCP.LS Banco Comercial Português SA |
| 3. | BNP.PA BNP Paribas SA |
| 4. | CBK.DE Commerzbank AG |
| 5. | DBK.DE Deutsche Bank AG |
| 6. | GLE.PA Société Générale SA |
| 7. | KBC.BR KBC Group NV |
| 8. | VLK.AS Van Lanschot Kempen NV |
| 9. | ABCB Ameris Bancorp |
| 10. | AMAL Amalgamated Financial Corp |
| 11. | ASB Associated Banc-Corp |
| 12. | AUB Atlantic Union Bankshares Corp |
| 13. | AX Axos Financial Inc |
| 14. | BANC Banc of California Inc |
| 15. | BANF BancFirst Corp |
| 16. | BANR Banner Corp |
| 17. | BCBP BCB Bancorp Inc |
| 18. | BFC Bank First Corp |
| 19. | BFST Business First Bancshares Inc |
| 20. | BHLB Berkshire Hills Bancorp Inc |
| 21. | BHRB Burke & Herbert Financial Services Corp |
| 22. | BKU BankUnited Inc |
| 23. | BMRC Bank of Marin Bancorp |
| 24. | BOH Bank of Hawaii Corp |
| 25. | BOKF BOK Financial Corp |
| 26. | BPOP Popular Inc |
| 27. | BRKL Brookline Bancorp Inc |
| 28. | BUSE First Busey Corp |
| 29. | BYFC Broadway Financial Corp |
| 30. | CADE Cadence Bank |
| 31. | CARV Carver Bancorp Inc |
| 32. | CASH Pathward Financial Inc |
| 33. | CATY Cathay General Bancorp |
| 34. | CBSH Commerce Bancshares Inc |
| 35. | CBU Community Financial System Inc |
| 36. | CCB Coastal Financial Corp |

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

37.	CFFN	Capitol Federal Financial Inc
38.	CFG	Citizens Financial Group Inc
39.	CFR	Cullen-Frost Bankers Inc
40.	CHCO	City Holding Co
41.	CLBK	Columbia Financial Inc
42.	CMA	Comerica Inc
43.	CNOB	ConnectOne Bancorp Inc
44.	COLB	Columbia Banking System Inc
45.	CPF	Central Pacific Financial Corp
46.	CUBI	Customers Bancorp Inc
47.	CVBF	CVB Financial Corp
48.	DCOM	Dime Community Bancshares Inc
49.	EBC	Eastern Bankshares Inc
50.	EFSC	Enterprise Financial Services Corp
51.	EGBN	Eagle Bancorp Inc
52.	ESQ	Esquire Financial Holdings Inc
53.	EWBC	East West Bancorp Inc
54.	FBK	FB Financial Corp
55.	FBNC	First Bancorp
56.	FBP	First BanCorp
57.	FCBC	First Community Bankshares Inc
58.	FCF	First Commonwealth Financial Corp
59.	FCNCA	First Citizens BancShares Inc
60.	FFBC	First Financial Bancorp
61.	FFIC	Flushing Financial Corp
62.	FFIN	First Financial Bankshares Inc
63.	FHB	First Hawaiian Inc
64.	FHN	First Horizon Corp
65.	FIBK	First Interstate BancSystem Inc
66.	FITB	Fifth Third Bancorp
67.	FLG	Flagstar Financial Inc
68.	FMBH	First Mid Bancshares Inc
69.	FNB	FNB Corp
70.	FRME	First Merchants Corp
71.	FSUN	FirstSun Capital Bancorp
72.	FULT	Fulton Financial Corp
73.	GABC	German American Bancorp Inc
74.	GBCI	Glacier Bancorp Inc
75.	GGAL	Grupo Financiero Galicia SA
76.	HAFC	Hanmi Financial Corp
77.	HBAN	Huntington Bancshares Inc
78.	HBNC	Horizon Bancorp Inc
79.	HFWA	Heritage Financial Corp
80.	HOMB	Home Bancshares Inc (Conway AR)
81.	HOPE	Hope Bancorp Inc
82.	HTBK	Heritage Commerce Corp
83.	HWC	Hancock Whitney Corp
84.	IBOC	International Bancshares Corp
85.	INBK	First Internet Bancorp
86.	INDB	Independent Bank Corp
87.	INTR	Inter & Co Inc
88.	ISTR	Investar Holding Corp
89.	KEY	KeyCorp
90.	LKFN	Lakeland Financial Corp

91.	MBIN	Merchants Bancorp
92.	MBWM	Mercantile Bank Corp
93.	MOFG	MidWestOne Financial Group Inc
94.	MTB	M&T Bank Corp
95.	NBBK	NB Bancorp Inc
96.	NBHC	National Bank Holdings Corp
97.	NBN	Northeast Bank
98.	NBTB	NBT Bancorp Inc
99.	NU	Nu Holdings Ltd
100.	NWBI	Northwest Bancshares Inc
101.	OCFC	OceanFirst Financial Corp
102.	OFG	OFG Bancorp
103.	ONB	Old National Bancorp
104.	OZK	Bank OZK
105.	PB	Prosperity Bancshares Inc
106.	PEBO	Peoples Bancorp Inc
107.	PFBC	Preferred Bank
108.	PFS	Provident Financial Services Inc
109.	PNC	The PNC Financial Services Group Inc
110.	PNFP	Pinnacle Financial Partners Inc
111.	PPBI	Pacific Premier Bancorp Inc
112.	PRK	Park National Corp
113.	QCRH	QCR Holdings Inc
114.	RBCAA	Republic Bancorp Inc
115.	RF	Regions Financial Corp
116.	RNST	Renasant Corp
117.	SBCF	Seacoast Banking Corp of Florida
118.	SBSI	Southside Bancshares Inc
119.	SFBS	ServisFirst Bancshares Inc
120.	SFNC	Simmons First National Corp
121.	SNV	Synovus Financial Corp
122.	SRCE	1st Source Corp
123.	SSB	SouthState Bank Corp
124.	STBA	S&T Bancorp Inc
125.	STEL	Stellar Bancorp Inc
126.	SYBT	Stock Yards Bancorp Inc
127.	TBBK	The Bancorp Inc
128.	TCBI	Texas Capital Bancshares Inc
129.	TCBK	TriCo Bancshares
130.	TFC	Truist Financial Corp
131.	TFIN	Triumph Financial Inc
132.	TFSL	TFS Financial Corp
133.	TMP	Tompkins Financial Corp
134.	TOWN	TowneBank
135.	TRMK	Trustmark Corp
136.	TRST	TrustCo Bank Corp NY
137.	UBSI	United Bankshares Inc
138.	UCB	United Community Banks Inc
139.	UMBF	UMB Financial Corp
140.	USB	US Bancorp
141.	UVSP	Univest Financial Corp
142.	VBTX	Veritex Holdings Inc
143.	VLY	Valley National Bancorp
144.	WABC	Westamerica Bancorporation

145.	WAFD	WaFd Inc
146.	WAL	Western Alliance Bancorporation
147.	WASH	Washington Trust Bancorp Inc
148.	WBS	Webster Financial Corp
149.	WSBC	WesBanco Inc
150.	WSFS	WSFS Financial Corp
151.	WTFC	Wintrust Financial Corp
152.	ZION	Zions Bancorporation National Association

40200 Financial Services

40210 Financial Services

40211 Financial Conglomerates

1.	FRHC	Freedom Holding Corp
2.	HTH	Hilltop Holdings Inc
3.	RILY	B Riley Financial Inc
4.	TREE	LendingTree Inc
5.	VOYA	Voya Financial Inc

40212 Mortgage Finance

1.	PBB.DE	Deutsche Pfandbriefbank AG
2.	BETR	Better Home & Finance Holding Co
3.	COOP	Mr Cooper Group Inc
4.	FMCC	Federal Home Loan Mortgage Corp
5.	FNMA	Federal National Mortgage Association
6.	GHLA	Guild Holdings Co
7.	PFSI	PennyMac Financial Services Inc
8.	RKT	Rocket Companies Inc
9.	UWMC	UWM Holdings Corp
10.	VEL	Velocity Financial Inc
11.	WD	Walker & Dunlop Inc

40213 Shell Companies

1.	AACT	Ares Acquisition Corp II
2.	AAM	AA Mission Acquisition Corp
3.	ANSC	Agriculture & Natural Solutions Acquisition
4.	BACQ	Bleichroeder Acquisition Corp I
5.	CCCX	Churchill Capital Corp X
6.	CCIR	Cohen Circle Acquisition Corp I
7.	CEP	Cantor Equity Partners Inc Class A
8.	CEPF	Cantor Equity Partners IV Inc
9.	CHAR	Charlton Aria Acquisition Corp
10.	DMYY	dMY Squared Technology Group Inc
11.	DYNX	Dynamix Corp
12.	EQV	EQV Ventures Acquisition Corp
13.	EURK	Eureka Acquisition Corp
14.	EVAC	EQV Ventures Acquisition Corp II
15.	GSRT	GSR III Acquisition Corp
16.	HOND	HCM II Acquisition Corp
17.	MBAV	M3-Brigade Acquisition V Corp
18.	RAAQ	Real Asset Acquisition Corp
19.	WLAC	Willow Lane Acquisition Corp

40220 Consumer Finance

40221 Credit Services

1.	EDEN.PA	Edenred SE
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2.	GLJ.DE	Grenke AG
3.	ALLY	Ally Financial Inc
4.	AXP	American Express Co
5.	BFH	Bread Financial Holdings Inc
6.	CACC	Credit Acceptance Corp
7.	COF	Capital One Financial Corp
8.	ECPG	Encore Capital Group Inc
9.	ENVA	Enova International Inc
10.	EZPW	EZCORP Inc
11.	FCFS	FirstCash Holdings Inc
12.	LMFA	LM Funding America Inc
13.	LX	LexinFintech Holdings Ltd
14.	MA	Mastercard Inc
15.	NAVI	Navient Corp
16.	OMF	OneMain Holdings Inc
17.	PRAA	PRA Group Inc
18.	PYPL	PayPal Holdings Inc
19.	QFIN	Qfin Holdings Inc
20.	SEZL	Sezzle Inc
21.	SLM	SLM Corp
22.	SOFI	SoFi Technologies Inc
23.	SYF	Synchrony Financial
24.	UPST	Upstart Holdings Inc
25.	V	Visa Inc
26.	WRLD	World Acceptance Corp
27.	WU	The Western Union Co

40230 Capital Markets

40231 Asset Management

1.	AMUN.PA	Amundi SA
2.	GBLB.BR	Groupe Bruxelles Lambert SA
3.	KBCA.BR	KBC Ancora SA
4.	MF.PA	Wendel
5.	SOF.BR	Sofina SA
6.	AAMI	Acadian Asset Management Inc
7.	AMG	Affiliated Managers Group Inc
8.	AMP	Ameriprise Financial Inc
9.	APAM	Artisan Partners Asset Management Inc
10.	APO	Apollo Global Management Inc
11.	ARES	Ares Management Corp
12.	BAM	Brookfield Asset Management Ltd
13.	BEN	Franklin Resources Inc
14.	BLK	BlackRock Inc
15.	BX	Blackstone Inc
16.	CG	The Carlyle Group Inc
17.	CNS	Cohen & Steers Inc
18.	EQH	Equitable Holdings Inc
19.	FHI	Federated Hermes Inc
20.	HASI	HA Sustainable Infrastructure Capital Inc
21.	HLNE	Hamilton Lane Inc
22.	IVZ	Invesco Ltd
23.	JHG	Janus Henderson Group PLC
24.	KKR	KKR & Co Inc
25.	NTRS	Northern Trust Corp

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

26. OWL	Blue Owl Capital Inc
27. PAX	Patria Investments Ltd
28. PFG	Principal Financial Group Inc
29. RJF	Raymond James Financial Inc
30. SEIC	SEI Investments Co
31. STEP	StepStone Group Inc
32. STT	State Street Corp
33. TPG	TPG Inc
34. TROW	T Rowe Price Group Inc
35. VCTR	Victory Capital Holdings Inc
36. VRTS	Virtus Investment Partners Inc
37. WT	WisdomTree Inc

40232 Capital Markets

1. FLOW.AS	Flow Traders Ltd
2. FTK.DE	flatexDEGIRO AG
3. AMRK	A-Mark Precious Metals Inc
4. BGC	BGC Group Inc
5. CIFR	Cipher Mining Inc
6. CLSK	CleanSpark Inc
7. DEFT	DeFi Technologies Inc
8. ETOR	eToro Group Ltd
9. EVR	Evercore Inc
10. FUTU	Futu Holdings Ltd
11. GLXY	Galaxy Digital
12. GS	The Goldman Sachs Group Inc
13. HLI	Houlihan Lokey Inc
14. HOOD	Robinhood Markets Inc
15. HUT	Hut 8 Corp
16. IBKR	Interactive Brokers Group Inc
17. IREN	IREN Ltd
18. JEF	Jefferies Financial Group Inc
19. LAZ	Lazard Inc
20. LPLA	LPL Financial Holdings Inc
21. MARA	MARA Holdings Inc
22. MC	Moelis & Co
23. MKTX	MarketAxess Holdings Inc
24. MRX	Marex Group PLC
25. MS	Morgan Stanley
26. PIPR	Piper Sandler Companies
27. PJT	PJT Partners Inc
28. PWP	Perella Weinberg Partners
29. RIOT	Riot Platforms Inc
30. SCHW	The Charles Schwab Corp
31. SF	Stifel Financial Corp
32. SNEX	StoneX Group Inc
33. TIGR	UP Fintech Holding Ltd
34. TW	Tradeweb Markets Inc
35. VIRT	Virtu Financial Inc
36. WULF	TeraWulf Inc
37. XP	XP Inc

40233 Financial Data & Stock Exchanges

1. DB1.DE	Deutsche Börse AG
2. ENX.PA	Euronext NV

3.	CBOE	Cboe Global Markets Inc
4.	CME	CME Group Inc
5.	COIN	Coinbase Global Inc
6.	FDS	FactSet Research Systems Inc
7.	ICE	Intercontinental Exchange Inc
8.	MCO	Moody's Corp
9.	MORN	Morningstar Inc
10.	MSCI	MSCI Inc
11.	NDAQ	Nasdaq Inc
12.	SPGI	S&P Global Inc
13.	TRU	TransUnion

40240 Mortgage REITs

40241 REIT-Mortgage

1.	ABR	Arbor Realty Trust Inc
2.	AGNC	AGNC Investment Corp
3.	ARI	Apollo Commercial Real Estate Finance Inc
4.	ARR	ARMOUR Residential REIT Inc
5.	BXMT	Blackstone Mortgage Trust Inc
6.	EFC	Ellington Financial Inc
7.	FBRT	Franklin BSP Realty Trust Inc
8.	KREF	KKR Real Estate Finance Trust Inc
9.	NLY	Annaly Capital Management Inc
10.	NYMT	New York Mortgage Trust Inc
11.	PMT	PennyMac Mortgage Investment Trust
12.	RC	Ready Capital Corp
13.	RITM	Rithm Capital Corp
14.	RWT	Redwood Trust Inc
15.	STWD	Starwood Property Trust Inc
16.	TWO	Two Harbors Investment Corp

40300 Insurance**40310 Insurance**

40311 Insurance Brokers

1.	AJG	Arthur J Gallagher & Co
2.	AON	Aon PLC
3.	BRO	Brown & Brown Inc
4.	BWIN	The Baldwin Insurance Group Inc
5.	CRVL	CorVel Corp
6.	ERIE	Erie Indemnity Co
7.	GSHD	Goosehead Insurance Inc
8.	MMC	Marsh & McLennan Companies Inc
9.	WTW	Willis Towers Watson Public Ltd Co

40312 Insurance-Life

1.	AFL	Aflac Inc
2.	BHF	Brighthouse Financial Inc
3.	CNO	CNO Financial Group Inc
4.	GL	Globe Life Inc
5.	GNW	Genworth Financial Inc
6.	JXN	Jackson Financial Inc
7.	LNC	Lincoln National Corp
8.	MET	MetLife Inc
9.	PRI	Primerica Inc

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

10.	PRU	Prudential Financial Inc
11.	UNM	Unum Group
40313	Insurance-Diversified	
1.	AGN.AS	Aegon Ltd
2.	AGS.BR	ageas SA
3.	ALV.DE	Allianz SE
4.	ASRNL.AS	ASR Nederland NV
5.	CS.PA	AXA SA
6.	NN.AS	NN Group NV
7.	TLX.DE	Talanx AG
8.	ACGL	Arch Capital Group Ltd
9.	AIG	American International Group Inc
10.	BRK-B	Berkshire Hathaway Inc
11.	IGIC	International General Insurance Holdings
40314	Insurance-Specialty	
1.	ACT	Enact Holdings Inc
2.	AGO	Assured Guaranty Ltd
3.	AMSF	AMERISAFE Inc
4.	AXS	AXIS Capital Holdings Ltd
5.	EIG	Employers Holdings Inc
6.	ESNT	Essent Group Ltd
7.	FAF	First American Financial Corp
8.	FNF	Fidelity National Financial Inc
9.	MTG	MGIC Investment Corp
10.	NMIH	NMI Holdings Inc
11.	RDN	Radian Group Inc
12.	RYAN	Ryan Specialty Holdings Inc
13.	TIPT	Tiptree Inc
40315	Insurance-Property & Casualty	
1.	AFG	American Financial Group Inc
2.	AIZ	Assurant Inc
3.	ALL	The Allstate Corp
4.	CB	Chubb Ltd
5.	CINF	Cincinnati Financial Corp
6.	CNA	CNA Financial Corp
7.	HCI	HCI Group Inc
8.	HIG	The Hartford Insurance Group Inc
9.	HMN	Horace Mann Educators Corp
10.	KMPR	Kemper Corp
11.	KNSL	Kinsale Capital Group Inc
12.	L	Loews Corp
13.	MCY	Mercury General Corp
14.	MKL	Markel Group Inc
15.	ORI	Old Republic International Corp
16.	PGR	The Progressive Corp
17.	PLMR	Palomar Holdings Inc
18.	PRA	ProAssurance Corp
19.	RLI	RLI Corp
20.	ROOT	Root Inc
21.	SAFT	Safety Insurance Group Inc
22.	SIGI	Selective Insurance Group Inc
23.	SKWD	Skyward Specialty Insurance Group Inc

24.	SLDE	Slide Insurance Holdings Inc
25.	STC	Stewart Information Services Corp
26.	THG	The Hanover Insurance Group Inc
27.	TRUP	Trupanion Inc
28.	TRV	The Travelers Companies Inc
29.	UFCS	United Fire Group Inc
30.	WRB	W R Berkley Corp
31.	WTM	White Mountains Insurance Group Ltd
40316 Insurance-Reinsurance		
1.	HNR1.DE	Hannover Rück SE
2.	MUV2.DE	Münchener Rückversicherungs AG
3.	SCR.PA	SCOR SE
4.	EG	Everest Group Ltd
5.	OXBR	Oxbridge Re Holdings Ltd
6.	RGA	Reinsurance Group of America Inc
7.	RNR	RenaissanceRe Holdings Ltd
8.	SPNT	SiriusPoint Ltd

45000 Technology

45100 Software & Services

45110 Information Technology Services

45111 Information Technology Services		
1.	ATO.PA	Atos SE
2.	BC8.DE	Bechtle AG
3.	CAP.PA	Capgemini SE
4.	FPG.PA	Union Technologies Informatique Group SA
5.	GLINT.LS	Glintt Global SA
6.	NBA.LS	Novabase SGPS
7.	NEDAP.AS	Nedap NV
8.	S30.PA	Solutions 30 SE
9.	ACN	Accenture PLC
10.	APLD	Applied Digital Corp
11.	ASGN	ASGN Inc
12.	AUR	Aurora Innovation Inc
13.	BR	Broadridge Financial Solutions Inc
14.	CACI	CACI International Inc
15.	CDW	CDW Corp
16.	CLVT	Clarivate PLC
17.	CNDT	Conduent Inc
18.	CNXC	Concentrix Corp
19.	CTSH	Cognizant Technology Solutions Corp
20.	DXC	DXC Technology Co
21.	EPAM	EPAM Systems Inc
22.	EXLS	ExlService Holdings Inc
23.	FI	Fiserv Inc
24.	FIS	Fidelity National Information Services Inc
25.	G	Genpact Ltd
26.	GDS	GDS Holdings Ltd
27.	GDYN	Grid Dynamics Holdings Inc
28.	GLOB	Globant SA
29.	IBM	International Business Machines Corp

30.	INGM	Ingram Micro Holding Corp
31.	INOD	Innodata Inc
32.	IT	Gartner Inc
33.	JKHY	Jack Henry & Associates Inc
34.	KD	Kyndryl Holdings Inc
35.	LDOS	Leidos Holdings Inc
36.	LZMH	LZ Technology Holdings Ltd
37.	MGIC	Magic Software Enterprises Ltd
38.	NABL	N-able Inc
39.	PENG	Penguin Solutions Inc
40.	PSN	Parsons Corp
41.	SAIC	Science Applications International Corp
42.	TTGT	TechTarget Inc
43.	VRRM	Verra Mobility Corp
44.	VYX	NCR Voyix Corp
45.	XRX	Xerox Holdings Corp

45120 Software

45121	Software-Application	
1.	CLA.PA	Claranova SE
2.	DSY.PA	Dassault Systèmes SE
3.	NEM.DE	Nemetschek SE
4.	QDT.PA	Quadiant SA
5.	SAP.DE	SAP SE
6.	TMV.DE	TeamViewer SE
7.	TOM2.AS	TomTom NV
8.	ADBE	Adobe Inc
9.	ADEA	Adeia Inc
10.	ADP	Automatic Data Processing Inc
11.	ADSK	Autodesk Inc
12.	AGYS	Agilysys Inc
13.	ALKT	Alkami Technology Inc
14.	ALRM	Alarm.com Holdings Inc
15.	AMPL	Amplitude Inc
16.	APPF	AppFolio Inc
17.	BILL	BILL Holdings Inc
18.	BL	BlackLine Inc
19.	BLKB	Blackbaud Inc
20.	BRZE	Braze Inc
21.	BSY	Bentley Systems Inc
22.	BTDR	Bitdeer Technologies Group
23.	BULL	Webull Corp
24.	CCCS	CCC Intelligent Solutions Holdings Inc
25.	CDNS	Cadence Design Systems Inc
26.	CHYM	Chime Financial Inc
27.	CRM	Salesforce Inc
28.	CVLT	Commvault Systems Inc
29.	CXM	Sprinklr Inc
30.	DAVE	Dave Inc
31.	DAY	Dayforce Inc
32.	DCBO	Docebo Inc
33.	DDOG	Datadog Inc
34.	DFIN	Donnelley Financial Solutions Inc
35.	DOCU	DocuSign Inc

36.	DSGX	The Descartes Systems Group Inc
37.	DT	Dynatrace Inc
38.	DUOL	Duolingo Inc
39.	DV	DoubleVerify Holdings Inc
40.	ESTC	Elastic NV
41.	FICO	Fair Isaac Corp
42.	FROG	JFrog Ltd
43.	FRSH	Freshworks Inc
44.	GRAB	Grab Holdings Ltd
45.	GTM	ZoomInfo Technologies Inc
46.	GWRE	Guidewire Software Inc
47.	HUBS	HubSpot Inc
48.	IDCC	InterDigital Inc
49.	INTA	Intapp Inc
50.	INTU	Intuit Inc
51.	JAMF	Jamf Holding Corp
52.	KARO	Karoo Ltd
53.	KC	Kingsoft Cloud Holdings Ltd
54.	LIF	Life360 Inc
55.	LYFT	Lyft Inc
56.	MANH	Manhattan Associates Inc
57.	MNDY	monday.com Ltd
58.	MSTR	Strategy Inc
59.	NATL	NCR Atleos Corp
60.	NCNO	nCino Inc
61.	NICE	NICE Ltd
62.	NOW	ServiceNow Inc
63.	OTEX	Open Text Corp
64.	PAYC	Paycom Software Inc
65.	PAYX	Paychex Inc
66.	PCOR	Procore Technologies Inc
67.	PCTY	Paylocity Holding Corp
68.	PDFS	PDF Solutions Inc
69.	PEGA	Pegasystems Inc
70.	PLUS	ePlus Inc
71.	PRCH	Porch Group Inc
72.	PTC	PTC Inc
73.	RNG	RingCentral Inc
74.	ROP	Roper Technologies Inc
75.	SHOP	Shopify Inc
76.	SNOW	Snowflake Inc
77.	SOUN	SoundHound AI Inc
78.	SPNS	Sapiens International Corp NV
79.	SPSC	SPS Commerce Inc
80.	SPT	Sprout Social Inc
81.	SRAD	Sportradar Group AG
82.	SSNC	SS&C Technologies Holdings Inc
83.	TEAM	Atlassian Corp
84.	TTAN	ServiceTitan Inc
85.	TYL	Tyler Technologies Inc
86.	U	Unity Software Inc
87.	UBER	Uber Technologies Inc
88.	UPBD	Upbound Group Inc
89.	VERX	Vertex Inc

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

90.	VMEO	Vimeo Inc
91.	WDAY	Workday Inc
92.	YOU	Clear Secure Inc
93.	ZM	Zoom Communications Inc
45122	Software-Infrastructure	
1.	ADYEN.AS	Adyen NV
2.	WLN.PA	Worldline SA
3.	ACIW	ACI Worldwide Inc
4.	AEVA	Aeva Technologies Inc
5.	AFRM	Affirm Holdings Inc
6.	AKAM	Akamai Technologies Inc
7.	APPN	Appian Corp
8.	ATEN	A10 Networks Inc
9.	AVDX	AvidXchange Holdings Inc
10.	AVPT	AvePoint Inc
11.	BASE	Couchbase Inc
12.	BOX	Box Inc
13.	CALX	Calix Inc
14.	CFLT	Confluent Inc
15.	CGNT	Cognyte Software Ltd
16.	CHKP	Check Point Software Technologies Ltd
17.	CLBT	Cellebrite DI Ltd
18.	CORZ	Core Scientific Inc
19.	CPAY	Corpay Inc
20.	CRWD	CrowdStrike Holdings Inc
21.	CRWW	CoreWeave Inc
22.	CSGS	CSG Systems International Inc
23.	CYBR	CyberArk Software Ltd
24.	DBX	Dropbox Inc
25.	DLO	DLocal Ltd
26.	DOCN	DigitalOcean Holdings Inc
27.	DOX	Amdocs Ltd
28.	EEFT	Euronet Worldwide Inc
29.	EVCN	EverCommerce Inc
30.	EVTC	EVERTEC Inc
31.	FAAS	DigiAsia Corp
32.	FFIV	F5 Inc
33.	FIVN	Five9 Inc
34.	FLYW	Flywire Corp
35.	FOUR	Shift4 Payments Inc
36.	FTNT	Fortinet Inc
37.	GCT	GigaCloud Technology Inc
38.	GDDY	GoDaddy Inc
39.	GEN	Gen Digital Inc
40.	GTLB	GitLab Inc
41.	INFA	Informatica Inc
42.	IOT	Samsara Inc
43.	KSPI	Joint Stock Co Kaspikz
44.	MDB	MongoDB Inc
45.	MQ	Marqeta Inc
46.	MSFT	Microsoft Corp
47.	NET	Cloudflare Inc
48.	NN	NextNav Inc

49.	NTAP	NetApp Inc
50.	NTCT	NetScout Systems Inc
51.	NTNX	Nutanix Inc
52.	NYAX	Nayax Ltd
53.	ODD	Oddity Tech Ltd
54.	OKTA	Okta Inc
55.	ORCL	Oracle Corp
56.	OS	OneStream Inc
57.	PANW	Palo Alto Networks Inc
58.	PATH	UiPath Inc
59.	PAYO	Payoneer Global Inc
60.	PGY	Pagaya Technologies Ltd
61.	PLTR	Palantir Technologies Inc
62.	PRGS	Progress Software Corp
63.	QLYS	Qualys Inc
64.	RAMP	LiveRamp Holdings Inc
65.	RBRK	Rubrik Inc
66.	RDWR	Radware Ltd
67.	RELY	Remitly Global Inc
68.	RPD	Rapid7 Inc
69.	S	SentinelOne Inc
70.	SABR	Sabre Corp
71.	SAIL	SailPoint Inc
72.	SNPS	Synopsys Inc
73.	STNE	StoneCo Ltd
74.	TAOP	Taoping Inc
75.	TDC	Teradata Corp
76.	TENB	Tenable Holdings Inc
77.	TLS	Telos Corp
78.	TOST	Toast Inc
79.	TWLO	Twilio Inc
80.	VRNS	Varonis Systems Inc
81.	VRNT	Verint Systems Inc
82.	VRSN	VeriSign Inc
83.	WEX	WEX Inc
84.	WIX	Wix.com Ltd
85.	XYZ	Block Inc
86.	ZS	Zscaler Inc

45200 Technology Hardware & Equipment

45210 Communications Equipment

45211 Communication Equipment

1.	AVT.PA	Avenir Telecom SA
2.	EKI.PA	EKINOPS SA
3.	TWEKA.AS	TKH Group NV
4.	AAOI	Applied Optoelectronics Inc
5.	ASTS	AST SpaceMobile Inc
6.	BDC	Belden Inc
7.	CIEN	Ciena Corp
8.	COMM	CommScope Holding Co Inc
9.	CSCO	Cisco Systems Inc
10.	DGII	Digi International Inc
11.	ERIC	Telefonaktiebolaget LM Ericsson (publ)

- 12. EXTR Extreme Networks Inc
- 13. HLIT Harmonic Inc
- 14. HPE Hewlett Packard Enterprise Co
- 15. LITE Lumentum Holdings Inc
- 16. MSI Motorola Solutions Inc
- 17. UI Ubiquiti Inc
- 18. VIAV Viavi Solutions Inc
- 19. VSAT Viasat Inc
- 20. ZBRA Zebra Technologies Corp

45220 Computer Hardware

- 45221 Computer Hardware
 - 1. ALLOG.PA Logic Instrument SA
 - 2. GUI.PA Guillemot Corporation SA
 - 3. ANET Arista Networks Inc
 - 4. CRSR Corsair Gaming Inc
 - 5. DELL Dell Technologies Inc
 - 6. HPQ HP Inc
 - 7. LOGI Logitech International SA
 - 8. NNDM Nano Dimension Ltd
 - 9. PSTG Pure Storage Inc
 - 10. QUBT Quantum Computing Inc
 - 11. RGTI Rigetti Computing Inc
 - 12. SMCI Super Micro Computer Inc
 - 13. SNDK Sandisk Corp
 - 14. STX Seagate Technology Holdings PLC
 - 15. WDC Western Digital Corp

45230 Electronic Equipment Instruments & Components

- 45231 Consumer Electronics
 - 1. ALJXR.PA Archos SA
 - 2. BSL.DE Basler AG
 - 3. AAPL Apple Inc
 - 4. AXIL AXIL Brands Inc
 - 5. KOSS Koss Corp
 - 6. SONO Sonos Inc
 - 7. TBCH Turtle Beach Corp
 - 8. UEIC Universal Electronics Inc
- 45232 Electronic Components
 - 1. BAR.BR Barco NV
 - 2. JEN.DE Jenoptik AG
 - 3. APH Amphenol Corp
 - 4. BELFB Bel Fuse Inc
 - 5. BHE Benchmark Electronics Inc
 - 6. CTS CTS Corp
 - 7. FLEX Flex Ltd
 - 8. FN Fabrinet
 - 9. GLW Corning Inc
 - 10. JBL Jabil Inc
 - 11. KN Knowles Corp
 - 12. LFUS Littelfuse Inc
 - 13. OLED Universal Display Corp
 - 14. OSIS OSI Systems Inc
 - 15. OUST Ouster Inc

16.	PLXS	Plexus Corp
17.	RAL	Ralliant Corp
18.	ROG	Rogers Corp
19.	SANM	Sanmina Corp
20.	TEL	TE Connectivity PLC
21.	TTMI	TTM Technologies Inc
22.	VICR	Vicor Corp

45233 Scientific & Technical Instruments

1.	BMI	Badger Meter Inc
2.	CGNX	Cognex Corp
3.	COHR	Coherent Corp
4.	ESE	ESCO Technologies Inc
5.	FTV	Fortive Corp
6.	GRMN	Garmin Ltd
7.	ITRI	Itron Inc
8.	KEYS	Keysight Technologies Inc
9.	MKSI	MKS Inc
10.	MLAB	Mesa Laboratories Inc
11.	NOVT	Novanta Inc
12.	ST	Sensata Technologies Holding PLC
13.	TDY	Teledyne Technologies Inc
14.	TRMB	Trimble Inc
15.	VNT	Vontier Corp

45234 Electronics & Computer Distribution

1.	RXL.PA	Rexel SA
2.	ARW	Arrow Electronics Inc
3.	AVT	Avnet Inc
4.	CNXN	PC Connection Inc
5.	NSIT	Insight Enterprises Inc
6.	SCSC	ScanSource Inc
7.	SNX	TD SYNEX Corp

45300 Semiconductors & Semiconductor Equipment**45310 Semiconductors & Semiconductor Equipment****45311 Semiconductor Equipment & Materials**

1.	AIXA.DE	AIXTRON SE
2.	ASM.AS	ASM International NV
3.	ASML.AS	ASML Holding NV
4.	BESI.AS	BE Semiconductor Industries NV
5.	SOI.PA	Soitec SA
6.	ACLS	Axcelis Technologies Inc
7.	ACMR	ACM Research Inc
8.	AMAT	Applied Materials Inc
9.	AMBA	Ambarella Inc
10.	AMKR	Amkor Technology Inc
11.	CAMT	Camtek Ltd
12.	COHU	Cohu Inc
13.	ENTG	Entegris Inc
14.	FORM	FormFactor Inc
15.	ICHR	Ichor Holdings Ltd
16.	IPGP	IPG Photonics Corp
17.	KLAC	KLA Corp
18.	KLIC	Kulicke and Soffa Industries Inc

Companies from Major US and European Indices, Grouped by Sector and Industry

19.	LRCX	Lam Research Corp
20.	NVMI	Nova Ltd
21.	ONTO	Onto Innovation Inc
22.	PLAB	Photronics Inc
23.	TER	Teradyne Inc
24.	UCTT	Ultra Clean Holdings Inc
25.	VECO	Veeco Instruments Inc
45312	Semiconductors	
1.	IFX.DE	Infineon Technologies AG
2.	MELE.BR	Melexis NV
3.	STMPA.PA	STMicroelectronics NV
4.	WAF.DE	Siltronic AG
5.	ADI	Analog Devices Inc
6.	ALAB	Astera Labs Inc
7.	ALGM	Allegro MicroSystems Inc
8.	AMD	Advanced Micro Devices Inc
9.	AOSL	Alpha and Omega Semiconductor Ltd
10.	ARM	Arm Holdings PLC
11.	AVGO	Broadcom Inc
12.	CEVA	CEVA Inc
13.	CRDO	Credo Technology Group Holding Ltd
14.	CRUS	Cirrus Logic Inc
15.	DIOD	Diodes Inc
16.	GFS	GLOBALFOUNDRIES Inc
17.	HIMX	Himax Technologies Inc
18.	INTC	Intel Corp
19.	LASR	nLIGHT Inc
20.	LSCC	Lattice Semiconductor Corp
21.	MCHP	Microchip Technology Inc
22.	MPWR	Monolithic Power Systems Inc
23.	MRVL	Marvell Technology Inc
24.	MTSI	MACOM Technology Solutions Holdings Inc
25.	MU	Micron Technology Inc
26.	MXL	MaxLinear Inc
27.	NVDA	NVIDIA Corp
28.	NVTS	Navitas Semiconductor Corp
29.	NXPI	NXP Semiconductors NV
30.	ON	ON Semiconductor Corp
31.	PI	Impinj Inc
32.	POWI	Power Integrations Inc
33.	QCOM	QUALCOMM Inc
34.	QRVO	Qorvo Inc
35.	RMBS	Rambus Inc
36.	SIMO	Silicon Motion Technology Corp
37.	SITM	SiTime Corp
38.	SLAB	Silicon Laboratories Inc
39.	SMTC	Semtech Corp
40.	SWKS	Skyworks Solutions Inc
41.	SYNA	Synaptics Inc
42.	TSEM	Tower Semiconductor Ltd
43.	TXN	Texas Instruments Inc
44.	VSH	Vishay Intertechnology Inc

45313	Solar	
1.	PS4.HM	Phoenix Solar AG
2.	S92.DE	SMA Solar Technology AG
3.	ARRY	Array Technologies Inc
4.	CSIQ	Canadian Solar Inc
5.	ENPH	Enphase Energy Inc
6.	FSLR	First Solar Inc
7.	NXT	Nextracker Inc
8.	RUN	Sunrun Inc
9.	SEDG	SolarEdge Technologies Inc
10.	SHLS	Shoals Technologies Group Inc

50000 Communication Services

50100 Telecommunication Services

50110 Telecommunication Services

50111	Telecom Services	
1.	DTE.DE	Deutsche Telekom AG
2.	FNTN.DE	freenet AG
3.	KPN.AS	Koninklijke KPN NV
4.	NOS.LS	NOS SGPS
5.	OBEL.BR	Orange Belgium SA
6.	ORA.PA	Orange SA
7.	PHR.LS	Pharol SGPS
8.	PROX.BR	Proximus PLC
9.	UTDI.DE	United Internet AG
10.	ATEX	Anterix Inc
11.	CABO	Cable One Inc
12.	CCOI	Cogent Communications Holdings Inc
13.	CHTR	Charter Communications Inc
14.	CMCSA	Comcast Corp
15.	FYBR	Frontier Communications Parent Inc
16.	GLIBA	GCI Liberty Inc - Series A GC
17.	GLIBK	GCI Liberty Inc
18.	GOGO	Gogo Inc
19.	GSAT	Globalstar Inc
20.	IRDM	Iridium Communications Inc
21.	LBRDA	Liberty Broadband Corp
22.	LBRDK	Liberty Broadband Corp
23.	LBTYA	Liberty Global Ltd
24.	LBTYK	Liberty Global Ltd
25.	LILAK	Liberty Latin America Ltd
26.	LUMN	Lumen Technologies Inc
27.	SATS	EchoStar Corp
28.	SHEN	Shenandoah Telecommunications Co
29.	SNRE	Sunrise Communications AG
30.	T	AT&T Inc
31.	TDS	Telephone and Data Systems Inc
32.	TIGO	Millicom International Cellular SA
33.	TMUS	T-Mobile US Inc
34.	VEON	VEON Ltd
35.	VOD	Vodafone Group Public Ltd Co

36. VZ Verizon Communications Inc

50200 Media & Entertainment

50210 Media

50211 Advertising Agencies

1. ALALO.PA Acheter-Louer Fr SA
2. ALNXT.PA Nextedia SA
3. ALREW.PA Reworld Media SA
4. DEC.PA JCDecaux SE
5. LOCAL.PA Solocal Group SA
6. PUB.PA Publicis Groupe SA
7. SAX.DE Ströer SE & Co KGaA
8. ADV Advantage Solutions Inc
9. APP AppLovin Corp
10. CRTO Criteo SA
11. IAS Integral Ad Science Holding Corp
12. IPG The Interpublic Group of Companies Inc
13. MGNI Magnite Inc
14. OMC Omnicom Group Inc
15. QNST QuinStreet Inc
16. STGW Stagwell Inc
17. TTD The Trade Desk Inc
18. ZD Ziff Davis Inc

50212 Broadcasting

1. IPR.LS Impresa SGPS
2. RRTL.DE RTL Group SA
3. SESG.PA SES SA
4. TFI.PA TF1 SA
5. NXST Nexstar Media Group Inc
6. TGNA TEGNA Inc

50213 Publishing

1. SNC.LS Sonaecom SGPS
2. DALN DallasNews Corp
3. IDWM IDW Media Holdings Inc
4. LEE Lee Enterprises Inc
5. NYT The New York Times Co
6. SCHL Scholastic Corp
7. WLY John Wiley & Sons Inc

50220 Entertainment

50221 Entertainment

1. BOL.PA Bolloré SE
2. EVD.DE CTS Eventim AG & Co KGaA
3. UMG.AS Universal Music Group NV
4. VIV.PA Vivendi SE
5. BATRK Atlanta Braves Holdings Inc
6. CNK Cinemark Holdings Inc
7. DIS The Walt Disney Co
8. FOX Fox Corp
9. FOXA Fox Corp
10. FWONA Formula One Group
11. FWONK Formula One Group
12. IQ iQIYI Inc

13.	LION	Lionsgate Studios Corp
14.	LLYVA	Liberty Live Group
15.	LLYVK	Liberty Live Group
16.	LYV	Live Nation Entertainment Inc
17.	MSGS	Madison Square Garden Sports Corp
18.	NFLX	Netflix Inc
19.	NWS	News Corp
20.	NWSA	News Corp
21.	PARA	Paramount Skydance Corp
22.	PLAY	Dave & Buster's Entertainment Inc
23.	PSKY	Paramount Skydance Corp
24.	ROKU	Roku Inc
25.	SIRI	Sirius XM Holdings Inc
26.	TKO	TKO Group Holdings Inc
27.	WBD	Warner Bros Discovery Inc
28.	WMG	Warner Music Group Corp

50222 Electronic Gaming & Multimedia

1.	ALATA.PA	Atari SA
2.	UBI.PA	Ubisoft Entertainment SA
3.	EA	Electronic Arts Inc
4.	GAME	GameSquare Holdings Inc
5.	NTES	NetEase Inc
6.	PLTK	Playtika Holding Corp
7.	RBLX	Roblox Corp
8.	TTWO	Take-Two Interactive Software Inc

50230 Internet Content & Information

50231 Internet Content & Information

1.	G24.DE	Scout24 SE
2.	PRC.PA	Artmarket.com
3.	PRX.AS	Prosus NV
4.	ANGI	Angi Inc
5.	BIDU	Baidu Inc
6.	BILI	Bilibili Inc
7.	BMBL	Bumble Inc
8.	BZ	Kanzhun Ltd
9.	CARS	Cars.com Inc
10.	DJT	Trump Media & Technology Group Corp
11.	GOOG	Alphabet Inc
12.	GOOGL	Alphabet Inc
13.	GRPN	Groupon Inc
14.	IAC	IAC Inc
15.	JOYY	JOYY Inc
16.	META	Meta Platforms Inc
17.	MOMO	Hello Group Inc
18.	MTCH	Match Group Inc
19.	NBIS	Nebius Group NV
20.	PINS	Pinterest Inc
21.	RDDT	Reddit Inc
22.	RUM	Rumble Inc
23.	SCOR	comScore Inc
24.	SPOT	Spotify Technology SA
25.	SSTK	Shutterstock Inc

26.	TBLA	Taboola.com Ltd
27.	THRY	Thryv Holdings Inc
28.	UPWK	Upwork Inc
29.	WB	Weibo Corp
30.	WBTN	WEBTOON Entertainment Inc
31.	YELP	Yelp Inc
32.	Z	Z: Zillow Group Inc
33.	ZG	Zillow Group Inc

55000 Utilities

55100 Utilities

55110 Electric Utilities

55111 Utilities-Regulated Electric

1.	ELI.BR	Elia Group SA
2.	AEE	Ameren Corp
3.	AEP	American Electric Power Co Inc
4.	CMS	CMS Energy Corp
5.	CNP	CenterPoint Energy Inc
6.	D	Dominion Energy Inc
7.	DTE	DTE Energy Co
8.	DUK	Duke Energy Corp
9.	ED	Consolidated Edison Inc
10.	EIX	Edison International
11.	ES	Eversource Energy
12.	ETR	Entergy Corp
13.	EVRG	Evergy Inc
14.	EXC	Exelon Corp
15.	FE	FirstEnergy Corp
16.	IDA	IDACORP Inc
17.	LNT	Alliant Energy Corp
18.	MGEE	MGE Energy Inc
19.	NEE	NextEra Energy Inc
20.	NWE	NorthWestern Energy Group Inc
21.	OGE	OGE Energy Corp
22.	PCG	PG&E Corp
23.	PEG	Public Service Enterprise Group Inc
24.	PNW	Pinnacle West Capital Corp
25.	POR	Portland General Electric Co
26.	PPL	PPL Corp
27.	SO	The Southern Co
28.	TXNM	TXNM Energy Inc
29.	WEC	WEC Energy Group Inc
30.	XEL	Xcel Energy Inc

55120 Gas Utilities

55121 Utilities-Regulated Gas

1.	ATO	Atmos Energy Corp
2.	BKH	Black Hills Corp
3.	CPK	Chesapeake Utilities Corp
4.	MDU	MDU Resources Group Inc
5.	NI	NiSource Inc

- 6. NJR New Jersey Resources Corp
- 7. NWN Northwest Natural Holding Co
- 8. OGS ONE Gas Inc
- 9. SR Spire Inc
- 10. SWX Southwest Gas Holdings Inc
- 11. UGI UGI Corp

55130 Diversified Utilities

55131 Utilities-Diversified

- 1. EDP.LS EDP SA
- 2. ENGI.PA Engie SA
- 3. EOAN.DE E.ON SE
- 4. RENE.LS REN Redes Energéticas Nacionais SGPS
- 5. RWE.DE RWE AG
- 6. AES The AES Corp
- 7. ALE ALLETE Inc
- 8. AVA Avista Corp
- 9. SRE Sempra
- 10. UTL Unitil Corp

55140 Water Utilities

55141 Utilities-Regulated Water

- 1. AWK American Water Works Co Inc
- 2. AWR American States Water Co
- 3. CWT California Water Service Group
- 4. HTO H2O America
- 5. MSEX Middlesex Water Co
- 6. WTRG Essential Utilities Inc

55150 Electricity Independent Power Producers

55151 Utilities-Independent Power Producers

- 1. ALVER.PA Vergnet SA
- 2. KEN Kenon Holdings Ltd
- 3. NRG NRG Energy Inc
- 4. TLN Talen Energy Corp
- 5. VST Vistra Corp

55152 Utilities-Renewable

- 1. ABO.DE clearvise AG
- 2. CAG0.HM Clere AG
- 3. ECV.HM Encavis AG
- 4. EDPR.LS EDP Renováveis SA
- 5. PNE3.DE PNE AG
- 6. VLTA.PA Voltalia SA
- 7. BEPC Brookfield Renewable Corp
- 8. CEG Constellation Energy Corp
- 9. CWEN Clearway Energy Inc
- 10. ENLT Enlight Renewable Energy Ltd
- 11. FLNC Fluence Energy Inc
- 12. ORA Ormat Technologies Inc
- 13. RNW ReNew Energy Global PLC
- 14. SAFX XCF Global Inc

60000 Real Estate

60100 Equity Real Estate Investment Trusts

60110 Diversified REITs

60111 REIT-Diversified

1. AAT American Assets Trust Inc
2. AHH Armada Hoffler Properties Inc
3. GNL Global Net Lease Inc
4. SAFE Safehold Inc
5. VICI VICI Properties Inc
6. WPC W P Carey Inc

60120 Industrial REITs

60121 REIT-Industrial

1. MONT.BR Montea Comm VA
2. WDP.BR Warehouses De Pauw SA
3. COLD Americold Realty Trust Inc
4. CUBE CubeSmart
5. EGP EastGroup Properties Inc
6. EXR Extra Space Storage Inc
7. FR First Industrial Realty Trust Inc
8. IIPR Innovative Industrial Properties Inc
9. LINE Lineage Inc
10. LXP LXP Industrial Trust
11. NSA National Storage Affiliates Trust
12. PLD Prologis Inc
13. PSA Public Storage
14. REXR Rexford Industrial Realty Inc
15. STAG STAG Industrial Inc
16. TRNO Terreno Realty Corp

60130 Hotel & Resort REITs

60131 REIT-Hotel & Motel

1. APLE Apple Hospitality REIT Inc
2. DRH DiamondRock Hospitality Co
3. HST Host Hotels & Resorts Inc
4. INN Summit Hotel Properties Inc
5. PEB Pebblebrook Hotel Trust
6. PK Park Hotels & Resorts Inc
7. RHP Ryman Hospitality Properties Inc
8. SHO Sunstone Hotel Investors Inc
9. SVC Service Properties Trust
10. XHR Xenia Hotels & Resorts Inc

60140 Office REITs

60141 REIT-Office

1. ACAN.PA Acanthe Développement
2. GFC.PA Gecina
3. MRL.LS MERLIN Properties SOCIMI SA
4. NSI.AS NSI NV
5. ARE Alexandria Real Estate Equities Inc
6. BDN Brandywine Realty Trust
7. BXP BXP Inc
8. CDP COPT Defense Properties

9.	CUZ	Cousins Properties Inc
10.	DEA	Easterly Government Properties Inc
11.	DEI	Douglas Emmett Inc
12.	HIW	Highwoods Properties Inc
13.	JBGS	JBG SMITH Properties
14.	KRC	Kilroy Realty Corp
15.	SLG	SL Green Realty Corp
16.	VNO	Vornado Realty Trust

60150 Health Care REITs

60151 REIT-Healthcare Facilities

1.	AED.BR	Aedifica SA
2.	COFB.BR	Cofinimmo SA
3.	CTRE	CareTrust REIT Inc
4.	DHC	Diversified Healthcare Trust
5.	DOC	Healthpeak Properties Inc
6.	HR	Healthcare Realty Trust Inc
7.	LTC	LTC Properties Inc
8.	MPW	Medical Properties Trust Inc
9.	OHI	Omega Healthcare Investors Inc
10.	SBRA	Sabra Health Care REIT Inc
11.	UHT	Universal Health Realty Income Trust
12.	VTR	Ventas Inc
13.	WELL	Welltower Inc

60160 Residential REITs

60161 REIT-Residential

1.	AMH	American Homes 4 Rent
2.	AVB	AvalonBay Communities Inc
3.	CPT	Camden Property Trust
4.	CSR	Centerspace
5.	ELME	Elme Communities
6.	ELS	Equity LifeStyle Properties Inc
7.	EQR	Equity Residential
8.	ESS	Essex Property Trust Inc
9.	INVH	Invitation Homes Inc
10.	IRT	Independence Realty Trust Inc
11.	MAA	Mid-America Apartment Communities Inc
12.	MRP	Millrose Properties Inc
13.	NXRT	NexPoint Residential Trust Inc
14.	SUI	Sun Communities Inc
15.	UDR	UDR Inc
16.	VRE	Veris Residential Inc

60170 Retail REITs

60171 REIT-Retail

1.	ECMPA.AS	Eurocommercial Properties NV
2.	LI.PA	Klépierre SA
3.	URW.PA	Unibail-Rodamco-Westfield SE
4.	WHA.AS	Wereldhave NV
5.	ADC	Agree Realty Corp
6.	AKR	Acadia Realty Trust
7.	ALEX	Alexander & Baldwin Inc
8.	BFS	Saul Centers Inc

9.	BRX	Brixmor Property Group Inc
10.	CURB	Curblin Properties Corp
11.	EPRT	Essential Properties Realty Trust Inc
12.	FCPT	Four Corners Property Trust Inc
13.	FRT	Federal Realty Investment Trust
14.	GTY	Getty Realty Corp
15.	KIM	Kimco Realty Corp
16.	KRG	Kite Realty Group Trust
17.	MAC	The Macerich Co
18.	NNN	NNN REIT Inc
19.	O	Realty Income Corp
20.	PECO	Phillips Edison & Co Inc
21.	REG	Regency Centers Corp
22.	SITC	SITE Centers Corp
23.	SKT	Tanger Inc
24.	SPG	Simon Property Group Inc
25.	UE	Urban Edge Properties
26.	WSR	Whitestone REIT

60180 Specialized REITs

60181 REIT-Specialty

1.	AMT	American Tower Corp
2.	CCI	Crown Castle Inc
3.	DLR	Digital Realty Trust Inc
4.	EPR	EPR Properties
5.	EQIX	Equinix Inc
6.	GLPI	Gaming and Leisure Properties Inc
7.	IRM	Iron Mountain Inc
8.	LAMR	Lamar Advertising Co
9.	OUT	OUTFRONT Media Inc
10.	PCH	PotlatchDeltic Corp
11.	RYN	Rayonier Inc
12.	SBAC	SBA Communications Corp
13.	UNIT	Uniti Group Inc
14.	WY	Weyerhaeuser Co

60200 Real Estate Management & Development

60210 Real Estate Management & Development

60211 Real Estate-Diversified

1.	TEG.DE	TAG Immobilien AG
2.	JOE	The St Joe Co
3.	STRS	Stratus Properties Inc

60212 Real Estate-Development

1.	AXR	AMREP Corp
2.	CCS	Century Communities Inc
3.	FOR	Forestar Group Inc
4.	FPH	Five Point Holdings LLC
5.	HHH	Howard Hughes Holdings Inc
6.	JFB	JFB Construction Holdings
7.	LPA	Logistic Properties of the Americas
8.	OZ	Belpointe PREP LLC
9.	SDHC	Smith Douglas Homes Corp
10.	SKYH	Sky Harbour Group Corp

60213 Real Estate Services

1. AT1.DE Aroundtown SA
2. DWNI.DE Deutsche Wohnen SE
3. LEG.DE LEG Immobilien SE
4. VNA.DE Vonovia SE
5. CBRE CBRE Group Inc
6. CHCI Comstock Holding Companies Inc
7. CIGI Colliers International Group Inc
8. CSGP CoStar Group Inc
9. CWK Cushman & Wakefield PLC
10. EXPI eXp World Holdings Inc
11. FSV FirstService Corp
12. JLL Jones Lang LaSalle Inc
13. KW Kennedy-Wilson Holdings Inc
14. MMI Marcus & Millichap Inc
15. NMRK Newmark Group Inc